

Received 14 October 2025, accepted 13 November 2025, date of publication 17 November 2025,
date of current version 21 November 2025.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3633780

APPLIED RESEARCH

SynthVal: A Framework for Validating Synthetic Medical Images

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The work of Dario Guidotti, Laura Pandolfo, and Luca Pulina was supported by EU Project SECURED, “Scaling Up Secure Processing, Anonymization and Generation of Health Data for EU Cross-Border Collaborative Research and Innovation,” under Agreement 101095717. The work of Alberto Gutierrez-Torre and Omar Lopez-Rubio was supported by SECURED under Agreement 101095717; in part by Spanish Ministry of Science (MICINN), the State Research Agency (AEI), and European Regional Development Funds (ERDF/FEDER) under Grant PID2021-126248OB-I00; in part by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, UE; and in part by the Generalitat de Catalunya (AGAUR) under Grant 2021-SGR-00478.

ABSTRACT Synthetic data is increasingly used in medical imaging to overcome data scarcity and privacy constraints. However, assessing the fidelity of synthetic images remains a critical challenge for ensuring their safe and effective use in clinical and AI applications. We present *SynthVal*, a Python-based framework for validating the quality of synthetic medical images through statistical comparisons in deep feature space. *SynthVal* extracts semantic image embeddings using transformer-based models and computes similarity metrics – including Fréchet Distance, Wasserstein Distance, and Kullback-Leibler Divergence – between real and synthetic data distributions. The framework is designed for modularity, scalability, and ease of integration into existing workflows via pip installation. We evaluate *SynthVal* using real images from the CSAW-CC dataset, and synthetic images produced by a model developed by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Our experiments systematically benchmark the influence of different feature extraction models and similarity metrics, providing practical insights for selecting validation strategies in medical image synthesis. *SynthVal* offers a reproducible and extensible solution for quality control in synthetic data pipelines.

INDEX TERMS Synthetic data validation, similarity metrics, health data, features extraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic data has become an increasingly important resource in medical imaging [1], offering solutions to critical challenges such as data scarcity, patient privacy, and class imbalance [2]. By generating artificial yet realistic samples, synthetic data enables the training and evaluation of machine learning models without relying exclusively on sensitive or hard-to-obtain real-world datasets. This is particularly relevant in domains such as mammography, radiology, and histopathology, where access to diverse and annotated clinical data remains a significant bottleneck for research and development [3].

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Thomas Canhao Xu¹.

Despite its growing use, the adoption of synthetic data in medical contexts raises essential questions about trust, quality, and fidelity [4]. Before synthetic datasets can be reliably integrated into diagnostic tools or AI-assisted workflows, it is crucial to validate their structural and statistical alignment with real data. Poorly generated synthetic images can introduce biases, degrade model performance, or lead to clinically misleading outcomes. As a result, robust validation methods are necessary to assess whether synthetic data accurately reflects the distributional characteristics of the real data it aims to replace or augment [5].

While several approaches exist for validating synthetic images [6] – ranging from pixel-level comparisons and human perceptual scoring to application-specific downstream evaluations – many lack generality, scalability, or reproducibility. In particular, pixel-wise metrics often fail to

capture high-level semantic or contextual differences, and handcrafted features may be inadequate for modern, high-dimensional medical data. Moreover, the lack of standardised tools for synthetic image validation hampers reproducibility and the consistent evaluation of generative models across studies.

In this paper, we introduce *SynthVal* [7], a modular, extensible, and open-source framework for validating the fidelity of synthetic medical images. Written in Python and available as a pip-installable package, *SynthVal* provides a structured approach to quality assessment through deep feature extraction and statistical distribution comparison. The framework is model-agnostic and supports multiple transformer-based architectures for extracting semantic representations from real and synthetic images. These representations are compared using established similarity metrics such as Fréchet Distance, Wasserstein Distance, and Kullback-Leibler Divergence to quantify alignment in the embedded feature space.

To evaluate the effectiveness of *SynthVal*, we conduct an experimental study using real mammographic images from the CSAW-CC dataset [8] and synthetic images generated by a proprietary model developed at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) [9]. Our analysis explores how different combinations of feature extractors and similarity metrics impact the detection of distributional differences between real and synthetic data. Beyond mammograms, Appendix presents additional experimental results obtained using another medical image dataset and a general image dataset. These supplementary evaluations demonstrate that, although *SynthVal* was primarily designed for medical data, its capabilities can be effectively applied to other types of images, provided that their features can be extracted using the supported feature extractors.

Our contributions are as follows:

- We present *SynthVal*, a reproducible and extensible Python framework for validating synthetic medical images using deep features and statistical similarity metrics.
- We benchmark multiple feature extractors and validation metrics to provide practical guidance for synthetic data evaluation.
- We make *SynthVal* available as an open-source tool¹ to support reproducible research in medical image synthesis and validation.

Overall *SynthVal* aims to support researchers and practitioners in the trustworthy integration of synthetic data into medical AI pipelines, offering a generalisable solution to a growing validation need in the field.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II introduces the foundational concepts related to synthetic data validation, with a particular emphasis on challenges and motivations within the medical imaging domain. Section III provides an overview of related work, highlighting existing

approaches and identifying current limitations that motivate the development of our framework. Section IV presents the *SynthVal* framework in detail, describing its overall architecture, the feature extraction methods it supports, and the set of similarity metrics it implements to evaluate synthetic data quality. Section V reports on the experimental evaluation, including a description of the dataset, the methodology used for generating synthetic data, the evaluation protocol, and a discussion of the results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper by summarising the key contributions and suggesting potential directions for future work.

II. BACKGROUND

Synthetic data is increasingly used in healthcare to address privacy concerns, augment datasets, and enable machine learning applications where real data is scarce or sensitive. As both the methods for generating synthetic data and the techniques for validating it have evolved rapidly, understanding the landscape of current approaches is essential for ensuring their safe and effective use. This section provides an overview of synthetic data generation techniques, ranging from traditional statistical methods to modern deep learning models, and discusses the key validation metrics used to assess the quality, fidelity, and practical utility of the generated data.

A. DATA GENERATION TECHNIQUES

Synthetic health data generation has evolved substantially, progressing from traditional statistical methods to advanced deep learning approaches. Early methods focused on structured health records using predefined rules and statistical distributions, whereas modern deep generative models can now produce highly realistic medical images and patient datasets that closely mirror real-world data.

Traditional techniques relied mainly on rule-based models and statistical sampling. Rule-based methods use expert-defined constraints and relationships between variables to generate coherent datasets, making them suitable for structured data such as electronic health records, where variables like age, diagnosis, and medication must remain consistent. Statistical sampling techniques, including bootstrapping and Monte Carlo simulations [10], approximate real-world distributions by generating new samples from probability models. While effective for simpler cases, these methods struggle to capture the complex, high-dimensional structures typical of medical data, especially images.

Deep learning introduced a significant advancement, enabling models that learn intricate relationships in health data while improving realism and diversity. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Diffusion Models have been especially impactful. GANs [11] use an adversarial generator–discriminator setup to iteratively refine synthetic outputs and have been widely applied to retinal scans, MRI images, and dataset augmentation [12]. However, they face issues such as mode collapse and unstable training. VAEs [13] instead learn

¹<https://github.com/AIMet-Lab/SynthVal>

probabilistic latent representations, offering more stable training and suitability for structured and time-series health data, though they often yield blurrier images. Hybrid VAE-GAN models attempt to combine the structured representation of VAEs with GANs' visual fidelity. More recently, Diffusion Models [14], [15] have emerged as a powerful alternative, refining noisy inputs through iterative denoising steps inspired by thermodynamics. They avoid mode collapse and generate diverse, high-fidelity images. Stable Diffusion [16], for example, achieves exceptional high-resolution synthesis in latent space and has been adapted to medical imaging tasks such as synthetic pathology slides and CT scans.

Beyond these core models, domain-specific adaptations continue to enhance data quality and realism. TimeGAN [17] integrates adversarial learning with recurrent architectures for sequential patient data, while StyleGAN variants [18] offer fine control over medical image synthesis, including disease-specific patterns. These developments underline the rapid evolution of generative techniques, with growing emphasis on ensuring statistical consistency and structural integrity with real-world data. As this work focuses on validating synthetic data regardless of the generation model, we do not discuss generative techniques in further detail.

B. VALIDATION METRICS

The validation of synthetic data is a critical step in ensuring its reliability and applicability, particularly in sensitive domains such as healthcare. Although synthetic data generation techniques have made significant progress – producing datasets that closely resemble real-world data – the main challenge remains the evaluation of whether these datasets preserve essential characteristics without introducing distortions that could lead to erroneous or misleading conclusions. Validation plays multiple roles: it confirms that synthetic data aligns with real data distributions, maintains structural and statistical fidelity, and is appropriate for training artificial intelligence models in clinical and research settings.

One of the central challenges in this context is assessing both structural and statistical fidelity. A high-quality synthetic dataset should replicate the relationships between variables found in the original data, while also avoiding overfitting, which could compromise privacy and introduce bias. *Structural fidelity* refers to the preservation of meaningful interdependencies between features, such as correlations between clinical variables or anatomical coherence in medical images. *Statistical fidelity*, in contrast, ensures that the distributions of individual features and their combinations in the synthetic data closely match those of the real data. To this end, statistical similarity measures – such as distributional comparisons, distance-based metrics, and evaluations based on statistical moments – are fundamental tools. These metrics provide quantitative insights into how accurately synthetic data captures the statistical properties of real datasets. Deviations in these properties may reduce the

practical utility of synthetic datasets, leading to misleading results in downstream tasks.

An equally important aspect of validation is assessing the utility of synthetic data for training machine learning models. Even when synthetic data appears statistically similar to real data, it must still enable the training of models that generalise effectively to real-world scenarios. If the synthetic data is poorly generated, models trained on it may perform well in artificial settings but fail to deliver accurate predictions in clinical practice. Therefore, depending on the intended use case, validation should also involve testing model performance: for instance, training models on synthetic data and evaluating them on real data. Additional techniques include training discriminative models – such as classifiers – to distinguish real from synthetic samples and comparing their accuracy, which can offer insights into the representational and functional utility of the data.

As synthetic data becomes more widely adopted in healthcare, the demand for rigorous and standardised validation frameworks continues to increase. Addressing this demand requires a multifaceted approach, combining *statistical similarity assessments*, machine learning performance benchmarks, and expert-driven validation protocols. Each of these elements contributes to ensuring that synthetic datasets are not only statistically and structurally accurate but also practically useful for medical research, education, and clinical deployment.

1) ML-BASED EVALUATION

Evaluating synthetic data through machine learning-based approaches offers a direct and practical way to assess its utility. By training models on synthetic data and testing them on real-world datasets, researchers can determine whether the generated data preserves meaningful patterns and relationships. If a model trained on synthetic data achieves accuracy, precision, and recall comparable to a model trained on real data, this suggests that the synthetic dataset effectively captures the underlying structure of the original data. This evaluation strategy is widely adopted in healthcare applications, where synthetic medical records or imaging datasets must support AI-driven diagnostics, predictive modelling, and automated decision-making.

When discrepancies arise between synthetic and real data, domain adaptation techniques can help bridge the gap. These methods refine the representations of synthetic data to better align with real-world data distributions, often by adjusting feature mappings or employing adversarial training strategies. For example, [19] introduced a Synthetic-to-Real Domain Adaptation Network that improved model generalization by minimizing domain discrepancies during training. In the context of medical imaging, domain adaptation is commonly applied to synthetic X-rays or MRI scans to ensure that models trained on artificial images generalize effectively to real ones – an essential requirement for AI-assisted diagnostics.

Crucially, the extent to which domain adaptation is required can serve as an indirect indicator of synthetic data quality. If significant adaptation is needed before models trained on synthetic data can perform well on real data, this may suggest that key properties of the original distribution are missing. Conversely, when synthetic data supports strong model performance with little or no adaptation, it offers further evidence of high fidelity. For instance, [20] showed that in certain cases, high-quality synthetic datasets enabled models to generalize effectively without additional processing, reinforcing their value as privacy-preserving alternatives in healthcare.

2) IMAGE-SPECIFIC EVALUATION

Validating synthetic medical images requires verifying that they preserve both structural and perceptual characteristics essential for diagnostic accuracy. Since medical images carry critical anatomical and pathological information, even subtle distortions or inconsistencies can undermine their utility in clinical and machine learning applications. Several metrics have been developed to assess the quality of synthetic images, focusing on structural integrity and perceptual realism. Beyond visual similarity, medical image validation also requires ensuring that synthetic data retain diagnostically relevant content, such as lesion boundaries, organ morphology, and texture patterns, that directly affect downstream algorithmic performance. Therefore, evaluation protocols often integrate both quantitative and qualitative assessments, including expert-based visual inspection or radiologist scoring, to complement automated metrics.

One of the most widely used structural validation metrics is the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [21], which quantifies the similarity between a synthetic image and its real counterpart by evaluating luminance, contrast, and structural components. Higher SSIM scores indicate better preservation of spatial patterns, making it a valuable tool for validating synthetic images in applications such as X-ray and MRI generation. However, despite its effectiveness in capturing perceptual distortions, SSIM may not always be sensitive to subtle details that are clinically significant. For example, small pathological signals, such as early-stage tumors, microaneurysms, or calcifications, may not drastically affect SSIM but can be crucial for diagnostic validity. Consequently, SSIM is often complemented by domain-specific analyses, such as segmentation overlap measures (e.g., Dice Similarity Coefficient or Intersection-over-Union), which verify that anatomical structures remain spatially consistent in synthetic data.

Another common metric is Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), which evaluates pixel-level differences between real and synthetic images. PSNR is widely used in image reconstruction and compression tasks to measure overall fidelity. Nonetheless, in medical imaging – where minor variations may have serious diagnostic implications – PSNR alone may not be sufficient to capture perceptual quality [22]. Two images with similar PSNR scores might still differ

in ways that are clinically meaningful, highlighting the need for more nuanced evaluation methods. Moreover, PSNR emphasizes absolute intensity differences, which can be misleading in modalities such as MRI or CT, where diagnostic interpretation often depends on relative contrast between tissues. As a result, perceptually motivated and task-oriented evaluation approaches have gained increasing attention to better reflect the clinical interpretability of synthetic images.

To address this limitation, the Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) metric [23] offers a deep learning-based approach to perceptual image comparison. Rather than relying on direct pixel-wise differences, LPIPS uses pretrained convolutional neural networks to extract feature representations that capture high-level visual characteristics across multiple layers. It then computes distances between normalized feature activations of two images and combines them through learned linear weights calibrated on human perceptual judgments. This design allows LPIPS to measure similarity in a way that aligns more closely with human visual perception than traditional metrics such as PSNR or SSIM. Nonetheless, LPIPS models are generally trained on natural image datasets such as ImageNet, which may limit their ability to capture domain-specific visual cues critical for medical interpretation. To address this limitation, recent research has proposed domain-adapted versions of LPIPS in which the feature extractor or perceptual weighting scheme is fine-tuned using medical imaging data, such as histopathology slides or radiology scans. These domain-specific adaptations improve the metric's alignment with clinical perception and enhance its ability to distinguish diagnostically relevant from irrelevant visual differences. In this context, its perceptual sensitivity is particularly valuable, as it helps preserve fine textures and subtle anomalies (such as microcalcifications in mammograms or slight tissue changes in MRI scans) that are often diagnostically significant. By leveraging feature embeddings learned from large-scale natural image datasets, LPIPS provides a more robust and perceptually grounded evaluation of image similarity than pixel-based alternatives. However, even in these adapted forms, LPIPS remains a measure of perceptual – rather than diagnostic – similarity, and its outcomes should therefore be interpreted within a perceptual rather than clinical framework.

In practice, combining SSIM, PSNR, and LPIPS enables a comprehensive assessment of synthetic image quality. Structural metrics ensure that spatial relationships and overall composition are preserved, while perceptual metrics capture finer-grained differences that may impact clinical utility. This multi-faceted approach is essential for validating synthetic images intended for diagnostic or research purposes in the medical domain.

3) STATISTICAL SIMILARITY METRICS

Statistical similarity metrics offer a foundational approach for evaluating the fidelity of synthetic data by quantifying

how closely its distribution aligns with that of real-world data. These metrics are particularly effective in capturing both global and local discrepancies between distributions, providing valuable insight into how accurately synthetic datasets approximate real ones. Below, we outline key statistical similarity metrics, presenting their mathematical definitions and explaining their significance in synthetic data validation.

a: WASSERSTEIN DISTANCE (WD)

Also known as the Earth Mover's Distance (EMD), the Wasserstein Distance [24], [25] measures the minimal cost of transforming one probability distribution into another. Unlike divergence measures that focus on pointwise differences, WD captures differences in both the shape and spread of distributions, making it well-suited for validating synthetic data when variances or modes differ [26].

For two probability distributions $p(x)$ and $q(x)$, the Wasserstein distance of order p is defined as:

$$W_p(P, Q) = \left(\inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma(P, Q)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d} \|x - y\|^p d\gamma(x, y) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

where $\Gamma(P, Q)$ is the set of all joint distributions with marginals P and Q , and $\|x - y\|$ denotes the distance between samples.

In the special case where $p = 1$, the Wasserstein-1 distance becomes:

$$W_1(P, Q) = \sup_{\|f\|_L \leq 1} \mathbb{E}_{x \sim P}[f(x)] - \mathbb{E}_{y \sim Q}[f(y)]$$

where the supremum is over all Lipschitz functions f with Lipschitz constant at most 1.

b: KULLBACK-LEIBLER DIVERGENCE (KLD)

KLD [27] quantifies the relative entropy between two probability distributions P and Q , measuring the information loss incurred when Q is used to approximate P . It is defined as follows:

For discrete distributions:

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q) = \sum_{x \in X} P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}$$

For continuous distributions:

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(x) \log \frac{p(x)}{q(x)} dx$$

Because KLD is asymmetric ($D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q) \neq D_{\text{KL}}(Q \parallel P)$), it may exaggerate certain mismatches and is often paired with symmetric alternatives such as the Jensen-Shannon divergence.

c: FRÉCHET DISTANCE (FD)

Fréchet Distance [28] measures the similarity between two multivariate Gaussian distributions by comparing their statistical moments. It is widely used in image synthesis evaluation, particularly in the form of the Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [29].

Let:

$$P = \mathcal{N}(\mu_r, \Sigma_r), \quad Q = \mathcal{N}(\mu_s, \Sigma_s)$$

where μ_r, Σ_r and μ_s, Σ_s are the means and covariances of the real and synthetic data features, respectively. The FD is computed as:

$$D_F(P, Q) = \|\mu_r - \mu_s\|^2 + \text{Tr} \left(\Sigma_r + \Sigma_s - 2(\Sigma_r \Sigma_s)^{1/2} \right)$$

where Tr denotes the trace operator.

d: ENERGY DISTANCE (ED)

Energy Distance [30] is a non-parametric metric that evaluates the discrepancy between distributions without assuming any parametric form. It is defined as:

$$D_E(P, Q) = 2\mathbb{E}[\|X - Y'\|] - \mathbb{E}[\|X - X'\|] - \mathbb{E}[\|Y - Y'\|]$$

where $X, X' \sim P$ and $Y, Y' \sim Q$ are independent samples from the real and synthetic distributions, respectively. The norm $\|\cdot\|$ is typically Euclidean. ED is effective for high-dimensional distribution comparisons.

e: KERNEL DISTANCE (KD)

KD [31] is derived from the Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD), a kernel-based statistical test that evaluates whether two samples originate from the same distribution. It is computed as:

$$\text{MMD}^2(P, Q) = \mathbb{E}_{X, X'}[k(X, X')] + \mathbb{E}_{Y, Y'}[k(Y, Y')] - 2\mathbb{E}_{X, Y}[k(X, Y)]$$

where $k(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a positive-definite kernel, such as the Gaussian RBF kernel. KD is robust and effective in non-parametric statistical testing scenarios.

f: MAHALANOBIS DISTANCE (MD)

MD [32] measures the distance of a point from a distribution while accounting for feature correlations. It is defined as:

$$D_M(x) = \sqrt{(x - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (x - \mu)} \quad (1)$$

where μ and Σ are the mean and covariance matrix of the reference distribution, and x is a sample point. MD is especially useful in high-dimensional settings where Euclidean distances are insufficient.

g: PRECISION (P) AND RECALL (R) SCORES

These metrics are designed to assess generative models in terms of sample fidelity and diversity. Precision measures the proportion of synthetic samples that lie within the real data manifold, while recall quantifies how well synthetic data spans the diversity of the real data distribution [33].

More formally:

$$P = \frac{\# \text{ of synthetic points within real k-NN neighbours}}{\text{Total number of synthetic samples}}$$

$$R = \frac{\# \text{ of real points within synthetic k-NN neighbours}}{\text{Total number of real samples}}$$

These scores are computed by estimating dataset manifolds using k-nearest-neighbour distances and provide a nuanced evaluation of generative model performance by balancing realism and variety.

III. RELATED WORKS

The validation of synthetic data is an increasingly active area of research. While numerous tools have been developed to generate synthetic datasets, far fewer focus specifically on evaluating their quality. This gap is particularly problematic in sensitive domains like medical imaging, where high fidelity is essential and even minor deviations from real data can significantly affect downstream tasks such as AI-assisted diagnosis. Over time, several frameworks have been proposed to address this challenge, aiming to assess statistical similarity, structural consistency, and machine learning utility of synthetic data.

One notable contribution in this area is *SynthEval* [34], an open-source framework designed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of synthetic datasets, particularly for tabular data. It incorporates a suite of statistical and machine learning-based metrics to assess both the utility and privacy-preserving aspects of synthetic datasets. However, its design is focused on structured data formats and does not extend to high-dimensional, unstructured data such as medical images, which pose unique challenges for validation.

Another relevant tool is *DataGene*,² which enables users to compare real and synthetic datasets by detecting similarities and discrepancies across features. While useful for structured data analysis, *DataGene* does not offer domain-specific adaptations for visual or perceptual data, limiting its applicability in contexts such as medical imaging, where anatomical consistency and subtle visual cues are critical.

SynthRO [35] adopts a practical approach to synthetic data validation by providing an interactive dashboard to compare model performance when trained on real versus synthetic data. This facilitates the assessment of downstream performance impacts, particularly in machine learning applications. However, the framework places less emphasis on detailed statistical or perceptual similarity, which are essential when validating image-based datasets.

A more general-purpose tool is *synthcity* [36], which includes a wide range of generative models and validation metrics. Although it provides a flexible architecture for synthetic data analysis, its core functionality remains focused on structured data, and it lacks specific capabilities for handling medical images.

The *SDMetrics*³ library, part of the broader Synthetic Data Vault ecosystem, also offers a robust set of statistical and utility metrics. Like many others, however, it is primarily designed for evaluating tabular datasets and does not address the validation needs of unstructured data such as medical images.

Similarly, the *table-evaluator*⁴ package provides light weight statistical comparisons between real and synthetic tabular data. While easy to use, its simple metrics do not capture the complexities of high-dimensional data, limiting its utility for image-based validation.

Collectively, these tools have contributed to more structured validation practices for synthetic datasets. However, most focus on structured, low-dimensional data and provide limited support for validating medical images, which require consideration of anatomical accuracy, perceptual realism, and clinical relevance.

In this context, *pyMDMA* [37] represents a domain-specific alternative tailored to healthcare. Developed within the AISym4Med project,⁵ a sister initiative to SECURED, *pyMDMA* focuses on statistical and structural validation of medical data. It employs a distinct set of metrics compared to our framework, offering complementary insights into the fidelity and usability of synthetic datasets in clinical scenarios.

It is worth noting that many of the aforementioned tools, including *SynthEval*, *SynthRO*, *synthcity*, and *pyMDMA*, have been published or released within the last two years. This recent wave of development underscores the growing importance of validation in synthetic data research and the need for domain-aware frameworks that can support the safe integration of synthetic datasets into real-world applications.

IV. FRAMEWORK

This section presents the Synthetic Data Validation Framework, called *SynthVal*, a *Python*-based framework designed to systematically assess the quality and fidelity of synthetic datasets. Although applicable to various data modalities, the framework is specifically tailored to medical imaging, where structural accuracy and statistical coherence are critical for both clinical interpretability and AI-based applications. *SynthVal* provides an automated and extensible pipeline to evaluate synthetic images by extracting high-level feature representations and computing similarity metrics that quantify alignment between synthetic and real data distributions.

The entire framework is implemented in *Python* and distributed via the *pip* package manager, allowing seamless installation and integration into existing research and development environments. This design choice brings several key advantages:

- *Interoperability and Flexibility*: Built on the *Python* ecosystem, *SynthVal* easily integrates with popular machine learning frameworks and data processing pipelines, enabling its adoption in diverse synthetic data validation tasks.
- *Extensibility*: The modular architecture of *SynthVal* allows users to incorporate new feature extractors and validation metrics, facilitating adaptation to evolving research needs and emerging technologies.

²<https://github.com/firmai/datagene>

³<https://github.com/sdv-dev/SDMetrics>

⁴<https://github.com/Baukebrenninkmeijer/table-evaluator>

⁵<https://aisym4med.eu>

FIGURE 1. Overview of the *SynthVal* package Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagram. For clarity, full details of `features_extraction.py` and `metrics.py` are omitted.

- *Scalability*: Compatibility with GPU-accelerated backends such as *PyTorch* [38] and CUDA ensures that *SynthVal* can handle large-scale image datasets efficiently, a key requirement for real-world medical applications.
- *Ease of Use and Accessibility*: With installation via *pip*, a well-documented API, and support for *Jupyter* notebooks, the framework offers a smooth learning curve for both researchers and practitioners.

Thanks to its structured, modular, and scalable design, *SynthVal* delivers a robust and extensible platform for evaluating the fidelity of synthetic medical images. By coupling deep feature extraction with rigorous statistical analysis, it enables comprehensive validation workflows suitable for healthcare and AI-assisted medical research. The use of standard *Python* tooling and practices further ensures that the framework remains accessible, maintainable, and ready to be integrated into broader research pipelines.

A. OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the *SynthVal* framework is designed to provide a modular and extensible solution for synthetic data validation, with a particular focus on medical imaging. The system is built around two fundamental tasks: extracting high-level feature representations from images and computing statistical similarity metrics to quantify the alignment between real and synthetic data distributions. These components are supported by utility and configuration modules that enhance flexibility, ensure consistency, and facilitate integration with external frameworks. A schematic

representation of the *SynthVal* architecture is shown in Figure 1. At the core of *SynthVal* are two principal capabilities: *feature extraction* and *metric computation*. The feature extraction module, implemented in `features_extraction.py`, processes medical images to obtain semantically rich feature embeddings. Unlike traditional methods based on pixel-level statistics or handcrafted descriptors, *SynthVal* leverages deep learning models – particularly transformer-based architectures and convolutional neural networks – to capture both structural and statistical properties of the images. A generic `FeatureExtractor` base class provides a standard interface for feature extraction, which is extended by multiple specialized extractor implementations.

Once feature representations are extracted, the validation step is carried out by the metrics module, implemented in `metrics.py`. This module defines a `SimilarityMetric` base class, which establishes a common interface for computing various similarity metrics. Implemented metrics include divergence-based measures, feature-space distance computations, and other custom metrics designed to quantify distributional differences between real and synthetic datasets.

To support these core functionalities, *SynthVal* includes utility and configuration modules, implemented in `utilities.py` and `configs.py`, respectively. The utility module provides essential functions and classes to streamline the validation workflow. A central component is the `FeatureDataset` class, a structured

container for managing extracted features from both real and synthetic images. This class facilitates storage, access, and partitioning of the datasets using configurable parameters such as test set proportion and random seed. Crucially, `FeatureDataset` ensures compatibility with the external `pyNeVer` framework [39], enabling the use of `pyNeVer`'s custom training loop for neural networks employed in metrics such as `FCNNAccuracyMetric`. This integration makes `FeatureDataset` a key element in *SynthVal*'s validation pipeline. Additional utility functions, including `get_stream_logger` for logging and `get_pil_image` for image handling, further support the smooth execution of validation tasks. Meanwhile, the configuration module (`configs.py`) defines a comprehensive set of parameters to ensure reproducibility and consistency across different validation experiments. This includes default values for metric computation and experimental conditions, contributing to the reproducibility of results.

The validation process in *SynthVal* follows a two-phase pipeline: *feature extraction* and *metrics computation*. During the feature extraction phase, both real and synthetic images are independently processed using deep-learning-based extractors to produce high-dimensional feature embeddings. These embeddings encapsulate meaningful structural and statistical characteristics of the images, serving as the basis for comparison. In the subsequent metrics computation phase, the extracted features are analysed using statistical similarity measures to assess how closely the synthetic data mirrors the real data. These metrics yield quantitative insights into the distributional alignment between datasets and help determine the fidelity of the synthetic images.

Figure 2 illustrates this workflow, showing how real and synthetic images are processed by the feature extraction module to generate embeddings, which are then evaluated by the metrics module. The modular architecture enables flexibility in selecting different extractors and metrics, supporting a wide range of validation needs and facilitating experimentation.

B. FEATURES EXTRACTION AND METRICS MODULES

The validation workflow in *SynthVal* is grounded in two interdependent modules: feature extraction and similarity evaluation. These components jointly establish a systematic process for assessing the fidelity of synthetic data. The feature extraction module transforms medical images into high-dimensional embeddings that encode semantic and structural information, while the metrics module quantitatively measures the alignment between real and synthetic feature distributions through a variety of statistical and learning-based approaches. Together, they provide a rigorous and extensible foundation for the quantitative validation of synthetic medical data.

a: FEATURES EXTRACTORS

The feature extraction module in *SynthVal* provides a unified and extensible framework for deriving high-level

representations from both real and synthetic medical images. Rather than relying on handcrafted descriptors or pixel-level statistics, it leverages pretrained deep learning models to obtain structured embeddings that encode semantic, spatial, and contextual properties of the input data. This approach ensures that validation is fully data-driven and consistent with recent advances in self-supervised learning and vision transformer architectures, which have demonstrated superior generalization across diverse imaging modalities.

The module is designed with flexibility and interoperability in mind, allowing different pretrained backbones to be integrated seamlessly within the same pipeline. Depending on the task and data characteristics, users can select from several state-of-the-art models. The *rad-dino* [40] extractor, pretrained on radiological datasets, is particularly suited for medical image validation tasks such as X-ray and MRI synthesis, as it captures fine-grained anatomical and pathological details. The *DINOv2* models [41], trained via self-supervised learning, provide general-purpose embeddings that encode rich semantic features without requiring labeled data. Meanwhile, NVIDIA's *MambaVision* architectures [42] introduce state-space mechanisms optimized for efficient and scalable visual processing, achieving strong representational power with reduced computational cost. The dimensionality and structure of the extracted features depend on the specific model variant used, offering flexibility for a range of analysis and comparison tasks.

At the core of this module lies a unified interface that abstracts the feature extraction process, ensuring consistent handling of input data, batch processing, and dataset-level aggregation across different models. This design allows new backbones to be integrated with minimal adaptation effort, supporting the continuous evolution of the framework as new pretrained models become available.

Finally, *SynthVal* builds on well-established libraries such as *HuggingFace Transformers* [43] for model loading and inference, *NumPy* [44] for numerical computation, and *Pandas* [45] for structured data management. This ensures a high degree of reproducibility, transparency, and computational efficiency throughout the feature extraction workflow.

b: METRICS

The `metrics.py` module in *SynthVal* provides a structured framework for evaluating the similarity between real and synthetic datasets. Since synthetic data aims to reproduce the statistical properties of real-world data, validation focuses on quantifying how closely the synthetic distribution aligns with the real one. The module supports a range of statistical and learning-based similarity measures designed to operate efficiently on high-dimensional feature representations. It relies on *NumPy*, *Pandas*, and *SciPy* for computation and data management.

At its core, the abstract class `SimilarityMetric` defines a common interface for comparing two sets of feature vectors, ensuring uniformity and extensibility across metrics.

FIGURE 2. Schematic representation of *SynthVal*'s Workflow.

Each subclass implements a dedicated strategy to measure the degree of similarity or divergence between real and synthetic feature distributions.

The `KLDivergenceEstimation` class estimates the Kullback–Leibler Divergence using the non-parametric method proposed by Pérez-Cruz [46]. It efficiently approximates information divergence in high-dimensional settings and belongs to the family of f -divergences, offering a principled way to quantify information loss between distributions.

The `WassersteinDistance` metric (Earth Mover's Distance) measures the minimal transport cost between two distributions, capturing geometric and structural differences in feature space. It provides a holistic view of similarity that considers both shape and spread, which is particularly relevant for image-based data.

The `EnergyDistance` [47] computes a statistical measure of similarity that captures differences in both central tendency and dispersion, offering robustness in cases where distributions vary in variance or shape.

The `MeanMahalanobisDistance` incorporates feature correlations to provide a scale-invariant measure of dissimilarity. By considering covariance relationships, it offers a more nuanced comparison than Euclidean-based distances, especially in complex, high-dimensional datasets.

Machine-learning-based approaches are also included, such as the `FCNNAccuracyMetric`, which trains a neural classifier to distinguish real from synthetic samples [39]. A 50% classification accuracy indicates maximum similarity (i.e., indistinguishable distributions), while higher accuracy values suggest greater separability.

Two widely adopted generative evaluation metrics are also implemented. The `FrechetDistance` compares the means and covariances of feature distributions, and when applied to embeddings from an *Inception* network [48],

corresponds to the standard Frechet Inception Distance (FID). Similarly, the `KernelDistance` computes a kernel-based similarity measure, equivalent to the Kernel Inception Distance (KID), providing robustness in high-dimensional spaces.

Finally, the `PRScores` metric computes precision and recall between feature manifolds, quantifying how well synthetic samples capture the diversity (recall) and fidelity (precision) of the real data. Supporting GPU acceleration, it enables scalable evaluation of large datasets and offers fine-grained insights into generative model performance.

Together, these metrics offer complementary perspectives – statistical, geometric, and discriminative – allowing *SynthVal* to perform a comprehensive and interpretable assessment of similarity between real and synthetic data.

C. ADVANTAGES

The *SynthVal* framework offers a comprehensive and extensible infrastructure for synthetic data validation, combining powerful feature extraction and flexible similarity metrics in a unified pipeline. By leveraging deep learning-based techniques, the feature extraction module captures semantic and structural properties of data, moving beyond superficial pixel-level comparisons. This is essential for assessing the fidelity and utility of synthetic datasets across a range of domains.

A key strength of the feature extraction module lies in its flexibility: users can select from a variety of advanced models – including self-supervised transformers, state-space architectures, and convolutional backbones – to tailor the extraction process to specific tasks and computational constraints. Its scalability is ensured by efficient batch processing and memory management, making it suitable for large-scale evaluations. Moreover, the standardized

FIGURE 3. Visual representation of a Diffusion Model. From Rombach et al. [49].

FeatureExtractor interface facilitates the integration of new models, ensuring adaptability to evolving deep learning trends.

Complementing this, the metrics module provides a robust framework for quantifying the similarity between real and synthetic data distributions. Built around the SimilarityMetric interface, it supports a diverse set of validation metrics – from statistical measures like KLD and Wasserstein Distance to feature-space metrics such as FD and learning-based methods like FCNN Accuracy. By operating on high-dimensional embeddings rather than raw pixels, it captures nuanced differences in distributional and semantic characteristics. Efficiency and scalability are central to the metrics module’s design. Many implementations leverage optimised routines in NumPy, SciPy, and PyTorch, with support for GPU and MPS acceleration where applicable. Like the feature extraction module, it is built for extensibility: new metrics can be integrated with minimal effort, ensuring that SynthVal remains aligned with best practices in generative model evaluation, especially in demanding fields like medical imaging.

Together, these modules position SynthVal as a future-proof, modular, and high-performance toolkit for the rigorous validation of synthetic data.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To evaluate the effectiveness of SynthVal in validating synthetic medical images, we conducted a comprehensive experimental assessment focused on mammograms. This case study explores the framework’s ability to distinguish between real and synthetic medical images by leveraging

its feature extraction and similarity metrics modules. The primary objective of this evaluation is to systematically analyse the performance of various validation metrics and assess the influence of different feature extractors on the fidelity estimation of synthetic data. The case study, developed in collaboration with BSC, uses real mammograms from the CSAW-CC dataset as reference data. This dataset provides a large collection of high-resolution mammograms, making it a suitable benchmark for evaluating the capability of SynthVal to distinguish between real and synthetically generated images. The corresponding synthetic mammograms were produced using a deep generative model developed by BSC, designed to generate realistic images while preserving the structural and statistical characteristics of authentic mammograms.

The evaluation follows a structured protocol. In the setup phase, we describe the dataset and the generative model employed to produce synthetic images. Next, in the results section, we report quantitative findings based on the computed similarity metrics, assessing how closely the synthetic images resemble their real counterparts. Finally, in the discussion section, we analyse the results, highlighting key observations and offering insights into the reliability of the validation framework within the context of this medical imaging modality.

By testing SynthVal on this focused medical imaging task, the experimental study aims to validate its robustness and provide evidence of its applicability to synthetic medical data. The insights obtained from the experiment offer a deeper understanding of how different feature extraction models and similarity metrics affect the evaluation of synthetic

image quality, ultimately supporting future advancements in synthetic data validation techniques.

A. SETUP

To systematically assess the quality of the generated mammograms, we extracted features from both real and synthetic images using our feature extraction submodule. Specifically, we employed multiple models from different feature extractor families to capture diverse high-level representations. The selected models included `dinov2-small`, `dinov2-base`, and `dinov2-large` from the *DINOv2* family, `MambaVision-S-1K` and `MambaVision-B-1K` from the *MambaVision* family, and `rad-dino`, which is tailored for medical imaging. By considering multiple feature extractors, we aimed to evaluate how different learned representations influence similarity measurements and to assess the robustness of our validation framework across various embedding spaces.

Once the features were computed, we applied all similarity metrics available in *SynthVal*, with the exception of the IS metric. This metric, along with the *Inception*-based feature extractors, was excluded because they are primarily intended for evaluating generative models trained on natural image datasets. Given our focus on medical imaging – where structural and semantic characteristics differ significantly from those of natural images – we prioritised feature extractors and metrics that are more appropriate for the domain. Nonetheless, we decided to retain them in the framework due to their historical relevance in synthetic image validation.

1) MODEL

The mammogram generator used in this study is based on a Stable Diffusion, specifically version 1.5. This model, built upon Latent Diffusion [49], has been pre-trained on a vast dataset of general images, enabling it to generate a wide variety of visual elements, including animals, humans, and other objects.

The architecture of this model comprises four key components, as illustrated in Figure 3:

- **Latent Encoder/Decoder (Red box):** This module transforms input images into a lower-dimensional latent space while preserving essential features. The reduced size of these latent representations greatly improves computational efficiency, while still enabling the original image to be reconstructed with minimal information loss.
- **Diffusion Process (Green box, upper part):** This module progressively adds noise to the latent representation through multiple steps, generating a structured noise pattern that retains key characteristics of the original image. This pattern is subsequently used during the denoising phase to synthesize a new image.
- **Conditioning Module:** This component integrates additional information, allowing the model to generate

images with user-defined attributes based on specified conditions.

- **Denoising U-Net:** A neural network responsible for transforming the structured noise back into a coherent image, effectively reconstructing meaningful visual content.

For the purpose of generating mammograms, the model was fine-tuned by adapting the Denoising U-Net component using images from the CSAW-CC dataset, which is introduced in the following section. In particular, the approach used is the same as shown in Montoya-del-Angel et al. [9] for mammogram generation. This fine-tuning process ensures that the synthetic mammograms preserve the structural and statistical properties of real mammographic images. The specific model used in the experimental evaluation is available on the Hugging Face platform.⁶

2) DATASET

The CSAW-CC dataset [8] is a large-scale collection of mammographic images acquired during breast cancer screening at Karolinska University Hospital in Stockholm, Sweden. Compiled under the supervision of Fredrik Strand at Karolinska Institutet, the dataset was developed to support AI-driven research aimed at enhancing breast cancer screening and diagnosis.

The dataset includes 1,103 cases of first-time breast cancer among women aged 40–74 years, recorded between November 2008 and December 2015. Of these, a random selection of 873 cases has been made publicly available. In addition, it comprises 7,850 healthy controls, selected from an initial pool of 10,000 individuals screened during the same period. Each subject is associated with multiple screening mammograms, including images from different time points, as well as metadata such as screening date and patient age. The dataset also includes pixel-level tumour annotations produced by expert radiologists, highlighting regions of interest in both diagnostic and pre-diagnostic scans. Complementary clinical cancer data, extracted from Karolinska University Hospital, provides further information such as diagnosis timing, tumour size, histological subtype, and lymph node involvement. To safeguard patient privacy, non-image data has been anonymised through categorisation and jittering techniques, preventing individual identification while preserving the statistical validity of the dataset.

Mammograms in the CSAW-CC dataset are categorised into two standard views used in breast cancer screening: craniocaudal (CC) and mediolateral oblique (MLO). The craniocaudal view captures a top-down projection, while the mediolateral oblique view provides an angled projection commonly used for its broader coverage of breast tissue. These two views ensure comprehensive imaging and are critical for clinical assessment. Each image is also labelled as either a left or right breast view, resulting in four distinct categories: R_CC, R_MLO, L_CC, and L_MLO. Here, “R”

⁶https://huggingface.co/fubukimaru/norther_1e6FullDataset210kSteps

FIGURE 4. Examples of mammograms: on the left a L_CC mammogram from the CSAW-CC dataset, on the right one of our generated images in the same configuration and large resolution.

TABLE 1. Computation times required for ED in the relevant cases. Column Feature Extractor ID lists the identifier of the feature extractor used. Column Evaluation ID indicates the specific evaluation setup. Finally, columns Mean and STD present the average computation time and standard deviation across different image sets, respectively. The symbol “-” denotes cases where all experiments for the corresponding sets failed to complete within the 1-hour timeout. All reported numerical values are expressed in seconds.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	same-real	350.39	3.51
dinov2-small	same-synth	350.56	4.43
dinov2-small	mix	1609.97	7.19
dinov2-base	same-real	745.93	4.13
dinov2-base	same-synth	745.71	3.03
dinov2-base	mix	3253.43	14.33
dinov2-large	same-real	1011.64	6.46
dinov2-large	same-synth	1008.32	4.47
dinov2-large	mix	-	-
MambaVision-S-1K	same-real	752.71	2.38
MambaVision-S-1K	same-synth	748.68	3.35
MambaVision-S-1K	mix	3271.99	17.97
MambaVision-B-1K	same-real	1009.63	1.70
MambaVision-B-1K	same-synth	1009.75	4.25
MambaVision-B-1K	mix	-	-
rad-dino	same-real	747.20	3.31
rad-dino	same-synth	748.49	4.75
rad-dino	mix	3263.24	10.93

and “L” indicate right and left views, respectively, while “CC” and “MLO” correspond to the craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique projections. For each of these four categories, the dataset contains a total of 24,696 images, offering a balanced distribution across imaging conditions.

The BSC deep generative model used to generate synthetic mammograms adheres to the same categorisation scheme to ensure alignment with the real dataset. It also supports generation at three different resolutions – small, medium, and large – to evaluate whether lower-resolution synthetic images can still retain diagnostically relevant features. This structured setup enables a systematic evaluation of how synthetic mammograms compare to real ones at varying levels of detail. For each of the four categories and three resolutions, we generated 24,696 synthetic images, thereby matching the quantity of synthetic and real data for direct comparison.

As a result, our experimental evaluation considered four distinct sets of real images (one for each category) and twelve distinct sets of synthetic images, corresponding to all combinations of categories and resolutions.

B. RESULTS

All experiments were conducted on a Dell PowerEdge R7615 server equipped with an AMD EPYC 9124 CPU, two Nvidia L40S GPUs, and 384 GB of RAM, running Ubuntu 24.04.1 LTS as the operating system. To ensure computational efficiency, a timeout of one hour was set for the computation of metrics on each dataset. For all metrics, the default parameters described in the previous sections were used, except for FCNNA, whose specific parameters will be detailed in the following discussion. It should be noted that a large amount of server RAM is not a strict requirement. In our experimental evaluation, memory usage never exceeded 32 GB. However, memory demands are directly related to the size of the datasets being analysed; therefore, for very large datasets, they may increase

FIGURE 5. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of ED values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. The x-axis consistently represents the ED values. To enhance clarity, the results from the *same* and *mix* evaluations are presented in separate plots, as their significant difference in scale would otherwise reduce readability.

substantially, making it necessary to use more powerful hardware or adopt techniques such as batch processing.

To better assess the behaviour of the metrics, we performed three complementary evaluations: the first compared features

TABLE 2. Computation times required for FD in the relevant cases. See Table 1 for more details about columns and measures.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	<i>same-real</i>	0.11	0.01
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.11	0.01
dinov2-small	<i>mix</i>	0.15	0.01
dinov2-base	<i>same-real</i>	0.38	0.03
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.39	0.02
dinov2-base	<i>mix</i>	0.46	0.03
dinov2-large	<i>same-real</i>	0.84	0.03
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.86	0.06
dinov2-large	<i>mix</i>	0.99	0.06
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-real</i>	0.39	0.02
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.35	0.02
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>mix</i>	0.46	0.02
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-real</i>	0.84	0.05
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.76	0.02
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>mix</i>	0.96	0.06
rad-dino	<i>same-real</i>	0.41	0.02
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.37	0.03
rad-dino	<i>mix</i>	0.46	0.03

from real images against other real features (labelled as *same-real*); the second compared synthetic features against synthetic features (*same-synth*); and the third compared real features against synthetic features (*mix*). The rationale behind this design is that a reliable metric should yield clearly distinct values for the first two cases compared to the third.

In the *same-real* evaluation, we computed each metric over 24 sets of real features, using half of the features as the first distribution and the other half as the second. In the *same-synth* evaluation, we applied the same approach to 72 sets of synthetic features. For the *mix* evaluation, we computed the metrics over 72 combinations formed by the 4 sets of real images, the 3 corresponding sets of synthetic images, and the 6 feature extractors.

The total number of computed metric values across all evaluations amounted to 1,344. Presenting these results in a numerical table would be impractical and overly complex due to the large number of entries. Instead, we opted for a graphical representation that effectively summarises the data while preserving interpretability. Given the number of variables involved in the evaluation setup, we found that the choice of feature extractor had the most substantial impact on the results. Therefore, we aggregated the other variables and focused on visualising the influence of different feature extractors on the computed metrics using histograms and kernel density estimation (KDE) plots. This approach offers a clearer understanding of how feature extraction affects the validation process while maintaining a comprehensive perspective on the overall behaviour of the metrics. It should be noted that the distributions shown in the following figures represent the computed metric values derived from the datasets, rather than the datasets themselves and that the patterns visible in these distributions arise because the sub-datasets are constructed according to specific criteria,

TABLE 3. Computation times required for KD in the relevant cases. See Table 1 for more details about columns and measures.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	<i>same-real</i>	2.23	0.03
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	2.21	0.02
dinov2-small	<i>mix</i>	2.28	0.02
dinov2-base	<i>same-real</i>	3.00	0.04
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	3.04	0.04
dinov2-base	<i>mix</i>	3.10	0.03
dinov2-large	<i>same-real</i>	3.91	0.03
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	3.91	0.16
dinov2-large	<i>mix</i>	3.95	0.28
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-real</i>	3.11	0.14
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	3.03	0.04
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>mix</i>	3.13	0.13
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-real</i>	3.74	0.05
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	3.81	0.10
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>mix</i>	3.80	0.10
rad-dino	<i>same-real</i>	3.04	0.02
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	3.08	0.14
rad-dino	<i>mix</i>	3.09	0.04

which leads to clusters in the metric space. No further random split were carried out beyond what was already discussed in the Setup subsection.

In the following, we present the results for each metric, accompanied by a brief discussion regarding the time required for their computation.

1) WASSERSTEIN DISTANCE

Unfortunately, this metric was too computationally demanding to be calculated within the one-hour timeout for any of the datasets considered. As a result, we are unable to provide further analysis or discussion on this metric using the CSAW dataset. Some supplementary experiments using smaller datasets can be found in Appendix.

2) ENERGY DISTANCE

While less computationally intensive than Wasserstein Distance, this metric still proved to be demanding in terms of computational resources. Specifically, during the *mix* evaluation, it failed to complete within the timeout when applied to features extracted using *dinov2-large* and *MambaVision-B-1K*.

In Table 1, we report the mean and standard deviation of the computation times required to calculate ED across the various feature datasets used in our experimental evaluation. As previously noted, results from different image sets were aggregated to obtain these statistical measures.

From our experiments, the two primary factors influencing computation time appear to be the number of samples – since the *mix* evaluation compares two full datasets of 24,696 samples, whereas the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations compare two halves of the dataset – and the choice of feature extractor, which directly determines the dimensionality of each sample. Furthermore, the relatively low standard

FIGURE 6. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of FD values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. See Figure 5 for more details.

deviation values indicate that the specific image sets do not significantly affect computational complexity. This aligns

with expectations, as computing metrics on extracted features rather than raw images eliminates dependency on image res-

FIGURE 7. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of KD values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. See Figure 5 for more details.

olution, with feature dimensionality being solely determined by the selected feature extractor. Overall, the results suggest

that ED exhibits a computational complexity that scales significantly with both the dimensionality of the feature

TABLE 4. Computation times required for KLD in the relevant cases. See Table 1 for more details about columns and measures.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	<i>same-real</i>	105.70	0.51
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	106.01	0.51
dinov2-small	<i>mix</i>	443.88	2.17
dinov2-base	<i>same-real</i>	163.14	0.40
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	163.01	0.17
dinov2-base	<i>mix</i>	662.68	3.56
dinov2-large	<i>same-real</i>	197.92	0.78
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	197.98	0.67
dinov2-large	<i>mix</i>	802.27	4.69
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-real</i>	133.98	5.70
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	162.75	0.41
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>mix</i>	591.60	14.89
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-real</i>	155.61	7.01
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	198.02	0.78
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>mix</i>	703.25	13.72
rad-dino	<i>same-real</i>	162.41	0.31
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	162.69	0.37
rad-dino	<i>mix</i>	663.40	5.84

space and the number of samples involved in the evaluation. Consequently, its application should be carefully considered for datasets with high-dimensional feature representations or large sample sizes, as these factors may lead to prohibitive computation times.

In Figure 5, we present the distribution of ED values computed using features extracted by different feature extractors across various image sets. To provide a clearer understanding of the metric's behaviour in different evaluation settings, we include both histogram and KDE plots, distinguishing between the *same-real*, *same-synth*, and *mix* evaluations. As previously mentioned, the computational complexity of ED prevented us from obtaining results for the *mix* evaluation when applied to features extracted using *dinov2-large* and *MambaVision-B-1K*. Consequently, the corresponding plots remain empty. In all other cases, the plots confirm that ED performs as expected, effectively distinguishing between datasets drawn from the same distribution – where values range between $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ – and datasets drawn from different distributions, which yield values between 3 and 25, depending on the feature extractor used. Notably, while all feature extractors enable ED to differentiate between real and synthetic data, the most pronounced separation is observed with features extracted by *dinov2-base* and *dinov2-small*. An additional observation is that feature extractors from the *MambaVision* family appear to distinguish between the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations – suggesting a capacity to recognise whether samples originate from real or synthetic distributions, even when drawn from the same type of data. However, the magnitude of this difference is extremely small, on the order of 10^{-4} , making it difficult to determine whether the effect is statistically significant.

Overall, the experimental results indicate that ED is a highly effective metric for distinguishing between real and

TABLE 5. Computation times required for MeanMD in the relevant cases. See Table 1 for more details about columns and measures.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	<i>same-real</i>	0.37	0.01
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.36	0.01
dinov2-small	<i>mix</i>	0.74	0.02
dinov2-base	<i>same-real</i>	1.12	0.01
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	1.13	0.02
dinov2-base	<i>mix</i>	2.24	0.03
dinov2-large	<i>same-real</i>	2.26	0.19
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	2.25	0.23
dinov2-large	<i>mix</i>	4.15	0.34
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-real</i>	1.11	0.01
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	1.11	0.03
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>mix</i>	2.26	0.04
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-real</i>	2.04	0.14
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	2.17	0.20
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>mix</i>	4.32	0.51
rad-dino	<i>same-real</i>	1.13	0.00
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	1.12	0.02
rad-dino	<i>mix</i>	2.30	0.05

synthetic data distributions. The computed values display a clear separation between samples originating from the same distribution and those from different distributions, reinforcing its reliability in synthetic data validation. However, the metric's computational complexity presents a significant limitation, particularly when applied to high-dimensional feature representations or large datasets. While ED successfully completed computations in most scenarios, its failure to process the *mix* evaluation for *dinov2-large* and *MambaVision-B-1K* underscores the need for careful consideration of its applicability in large-scale evaluations. Nonetheless, ED remains a valuable tool for assessing distributional similarity, especially in cases where computational resources are not a limiting factor.

3) FRECHET DISTANCE

This metric is significantly less computationally demanding than ED and similar methods, as demonstrated in Table 2. Comparing Tables 2 and 1, an interesting observation emerges: while the variation in computational time across different feature extractors follows a similar trend – albeit on a much smaller scale – the impact of the number of samples on computational complexity is considerably lower for FD compared to ED.

This metric is significantly less computationally demanding than ED and similar methods and, particularly, while the variation in computational time across different feature extractors follows a similar trend – albeit on a much smaller scale – the impact of the number of samples on computational complexity is considerably lower for FD compared to ED.

Specifically, in the case of ED, the computational time for the *mix* evaluation is approximately four times that of the *same* evaluations, whereas for FD, the corresponding

FIGURE 8. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of KLD values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. See Figure 5 for more details.

increase is at most 30%. This indicates that FD is far less sensitive to dataset size, making it a highly efficient choice for

large-scale evaluations involving high-dimensional feature representations.

FIGURE 9. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of MeanMD values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. See Figure 5 for more details.

In Figure 6, we illustrate the distribution of FD values computed using features extracted by different feature extractors

across various image sets. To provide a clearer understanding of the metric’s behaviour in different evaluation settings,

FIGURE 10. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of P-Score values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. The positions of *mix* and *same* are inverted to maintain consistency along the x-axis, since for the PR-Score higher values indicate greater similarity. See Figure 5 for more details.

we present both histogram and KDE plots, distinguishing between the *same-real*, *same-synth*, and *mix* evaluations.

Similar to the results observed for ED, the plots confirm that FD performs as expected, effectively distinguishing

FIGURE 11. Histograms and KDE plots depicting the distribution of R-Score values computed using features extracted from different feature extractors. See Figure 10 for more details.

between datasets drawn from the same distribution – where values range approximately between 0 and 13 –

and datasets originating from different distributions, which yield values ranging from about 15 to 1400, depending on

TABLE 6. Computation times required for PR-Scores in the relevant cases. See Table 1 for more details about columns and measures.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	<i>same-real</i>	0.33	0.00
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.32	0.02
dinov2-small	<i>mix</i>	0.46	0.01
dinov2-base	<i>same-real</i>	0.34	0.00
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.33	0.02
dinov2-base	<i>mix</i>	0.53	0.02
dinov2-large	<i>same-real</i>	0.33	0.01
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.32	0.02
dinov2-large	<i>mix</i>	0.59	0.02
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-real</i>	0.32	0.02
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.32	0.02
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>mix</i>	0.53	0.01
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-real</i>	0.34	0.00
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.33	0.02
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>mix</i>	0.58	0.01
rad-dino	<i>same-real</i>	0.32	0.02
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.32	0.02
rad-dino	<i>mix</i>	0.53	0.02

the feature extractor used. Notably, all feature extractors enable FD to clearly differentiate between real and synthetic data. Additionally, feature extractors from the *MambaVision* family once again demonstrate the ability to distinguish between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations, although the magnitude of this difference remains relatively small.

Overall, the experimental results demonstrate that FD is a highly effective and computationally efficient metric for distinguishing between real and synthetic data distributions. The computed values for *same* and *mix* evaluations exhibit a clear and substantial separation, confirming its reliability in assessing distributional similarity. Unlike ED, FD shows markedly reduced sensitivity to dataset size, making it well-suited for large-scale evaluations, even when applied to high-dimensional feature representations. Moreover, while all feature extractors enable FD to differentiate between real and synthetic data, the differences observed between *same-real* and *same-synth* results when using *MambaVision* feature extractors suggest a potential capability of capturing subtle distinctions in feature distributions. This further reinforces the utility of FD as a robust and efficient metric for validating synthetic data.

4) KERNEL DISTANCE

Similar to FD, this metric exhibits relatively low computational complexity, as shown in Table 3. A comparison between Tables 3 and 2 reveals that while KD generally requires slightly more time than FD, it is even less affected by the number of samples in the dataset.

Specifically, the increase in computation time between *same* and *mix* evaluations is approximately 3% for KD, compared to 30% for FD. This suggests that KD is highly scalable and particularly well suited for evaluating large-scale datasets.

TABLE 7. Computation times required for FCNNA in the relevant cases. See Table 1 for more details about columns and measures.

Feature Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Mean	STD
dinov2-small	<i>same-real</i>	60.51	3.36
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	60.76	3.13
dinov2-small	<i>mix</i>	121.37	6.16
dinov2-base	<i>same-real</i>	95.72	5.92
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	94.79	6.14
dinov2-base	<i>mix</i>	191.45	13.01
dinov2-large	<i>same-real</i>	126.61	1.35
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	115.22	8.41
dinov2-large	<i>mix</i>	234.73	16.88
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-real</i>	101.55	1.31
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	95.47	6.76
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>mix</i>	190.03	13.11
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-real</i>	116.89	7.59
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	121.15	8.49
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>mix</i>	227.02	15.59
rad-dino	<i>same-real</i>	91.76	5.68
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	94.12	6.57
rad-dino	<i>mix</i>	193.54	12.18

In Figure 7, we present the distribution of KD values computed using features extracted by different feature extractors across various image sets, following the same methodology as for the previous metrics. Interestingly, the results for this metric show notable differences compared to previous ones. While KD behaves as expected for features extracted using the *DINOv2* family – exhibiting a clear distinction between the *same* and *mix* evaluations – the separation is significantly less pronounced for features obtained using the *MambaVision* extractors and *rad-dino*. Nevertheless, even though the scale of values is smaller than for previously analysed metrics, KD still successfully differentiates between the evaluation settings across all feature extractors. In particular, values range between $-5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ for *same* evaluations, and between 0.04 and 0.5 for the *mix* evaluation. Moreover, in contrast to some previously examined metrics, none of the feature extractors exhibit a noticeable difference between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations.

Overall, KD proves to be a computationally efficient metric with minimal sensitivity to dataset size, making it suitable for large-scale synthetic data evaluations. While it effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic data for *DINOv2* features, the distinction is much less evident for *MambaVision* and *rad-dino* extractors. Despite this reduced separation, KD still provides a clear difference between the *same* and *mix* evaluations across all feature extractors, albeit on a smaller numerical scale compared to other metrics. This suggests that KD remains a valuable tool for measuring similarity in high-dimensional feature spaces, though its effectiveness may be more dependent on the choice of feature extractor than metrics such as ED or FD. Additionally, the absence of a difference between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations suggests that KD may be less sensitive to subtle distributional variations within real or synthetic datasets.

5) KULLBACK–LEIBLER DIVERGENCE

With this metric, we observe a return to higher computational complexity compared to FD and KD, although it remains less demanding than ED. As shown in Table 4, the computational time required for KLD is highly dependent on dataset size, as evidenced by the substantial increase in computation time between the *same* and *mix* evaluations. However, an interesting distinction emerges when comparing it to ED: while ED exhibits a strong dependence on feature dimensionality – doubling in computation time between *dinov2-small* and *dinov2-base* – KLD shows a more moderate increase of approximately 50% for the same comparison. This suggests that, in terms of computational efficiency, KLD may be a preferable choice over ED for datasets with high-dimensional feature representations, as it scales more favourably with feature dimensionality while still maintaining a clear sensitivity to dataset size.

In Figure 8, we present the distribution of KLD values computed using features extracted by different feature extractors across various image sets, following the same methodology as for the previous metrics. As observed with ED and FD, the plots confirm that KLD performs as expected, effectively differentiating between datasets drawn from the same distribution – where values range approximately between -2 and 2 – and datasets originating from different distributions, which exhibit values spanning from around 130 to beyond 3000, depending on the feature extractor used. Notably, while KLD does not appear to distinguish between the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations regardless of the feature extractor employed, the extractors from the *MambaVision* family seem to yield feature representations that allow for a particularly clear separation between the *same* and *mix* evaluations – thus effectively differentiating real from synthetic data. Nevertheless, Figure 8 clearly shows that all feature extractors produce representations that enable a strong distinction between real and synthetic distributions.

Overall, KLD proves to be a reliable metric for evaluating the similarity between real and synthetic data distributions. Its ability to clearly separate *same* and *mix* evaluations across all feature extractors confirms its effectiveness in identifying differences between distributions. Moreover, while its computational complexity is higher than that of FD and KD, it remains more scalable than ED, particularly in terms of feature dimensionality. This makes KLD a practical choice for large datasets with high-dimensional feature representations. Additionally, the results suggest that feature extractors from the *MambaVision* family provide the strongest distinction between real and synthetic data when using this metric. However, since KLD does not differentiate between the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations, it may be less informative in capturing finer variations within real and synthetic distributions.

6) MEAN MAHALANOBIS DISTANCE

The computational demands of this metric appear to be on the same order of magnitude as FD and KD, and its computation time seems to be significantly influenced by both the number of samples in the dataset and their dimensionality. However, while an increase in the number of samples leads to a roughly linear increase in computational complexity – as evidenced by the fact that the *mix* evaluation involves twice the number of samples as the *same* evaluations, resulting in a corresponding doubling of computation time – the relationship between feature dimensionality and computational complexity appears to be non-linear. Specifically, although *dinov2-small* and *dinov2-base* produce feature representations with twice the dimensionality, the associated computation time more than triples.

Overall, MeanMD maintains a sufficiently low computational complexity to be applicable even for very large datasets. However, it is important to consider its non-linear scaling with feature dimensionality.

In Figure 9, we illustrate the distribution of MeanMD values computed using features extracted by different feature extractors across various image sets, following the same methodology applied to the previous metrics. The results indicate that MeanMD exhibits a lower capacity to clearly differentiate between the *same* and *mix* evaluations compared to the other metrics assessed so far. Specifically, for all feature extractors except *dinov2-large*, there is a noticeable overlap between the values obtained for the *same-synth* and *mix* evaluations. This suggests that MeanMD does not consistently distinguish between data originating from the same distribution and data drawn from different distributions, potentially limiting its reliability in evaluating synthetic data similarity. However, an interesting observation emerges when considering the distinction between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations. Across all feature extractors, MeanMD consistently differentiates these two cases, with an even more pronounced separation between *same-real* and *mix*. This pattern suggests that the metric may be more effective in capturing internal structural differences within distributions, rather than providing a strong overall distinction between real and synthetic data. Despite this potential, the results indicate that MeanMD does not offer a particularly high level of reliability for differentiating real from synthetic images in a consistent and robust manner.

Overall, while MeanMD maintains a relatively low computational complexity, its effectiveness in distinguishing between real and synthetic data appears to be more limited compared to other metrics. Although it consistently differentiates between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations, the significant overlap between *same-synth* and *mix* evaluations suggests that it does not reliably separate synthetic data from real distributions. Instead, its primary strength seems to lie in capturing internal structural variations within a given distribution, rather than providing a robust measure of overall

FIGURE 12. Comparison of execution times for each validation metric using a performance profile plot. Each curve represents a validation metric and shows execution times (on a logarithmic scale) sorted in ascending order across individual instances. The red dashed line indicates the timeout threshold set at 3600 seconds. The reported times were measured using Python's `time.perf_counter()` function and should be regarded as general indicators rather than formal benchmark results.

distributional similarity. Consequently, while MeanMD may still offer useful insights into certain dataset properties, its limitations should be carefully considered when selecting metrics for synthetic data validation.

7) PRECISION AND RECALL SCORES

The computational requirements of this metric appear to be on the same order of magnitude as FD. However, unlike most of the other metrics considered so far, its complexity remains largely unaffected by the dimensionality of the data. This characteristic sets it apart, as it ensures stable computational performance even when handling high-dimensional feature representations. Nevertheless, the metric does exhibit a linear increase in complexity concerning the number of samples in the dataset, meaning that larger datasets lead to proportionally longer computation times.

Overall, PR-Scores emerge as a highly efficient metric in terms of computational resource consumption, making them particularly well-suited for datasets with very high-dimensional feature representations. Additionally, a notable advantage of this metric is that its implementation is designed to take advantage of GPU acceleration, further enhancing its efficiency and scalability for large-scale evaluations.

Since P-Score and R-Score exhibit highly similar behaviour, we analyse their results together, as shown in Figures 10 and 11. As with the previously discussed metrics, these plots illustrate the distribution of computed values across various image sets using different feature extractors. The results demonstrate a strong ability to distinguish between the *same* and *mix* evaluations across all feature

extractors. Additionally, feature representations derived from the *MambaVision* models appear to further enhance the metrics' ability to differentiate between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations. More generally, these feature extractors seem particularly well-suited for computing these metrics, reinforcing their effectiveness in capturing distributional differences between real and synthetic data.

Overall, PR-Scores prove to be highly effective for distinguishing real from synthetic data, consistently separating *same* and *mix* evaluations across all feature extractors. The enhanced distinction observed with *MambaVision* features highlights the impact of feature selection on metric performance. Given their low computational cost, scalability, and efficient GPU implementation, PR-Scores are well-suited for large-scale synthetic data validation.

8) FCNN ACCURACY

As previously mentioned, custom parameters were used for the FCNNA metric in our experiments. Specifically, the FCNN constructed for this metric consisted of two hidden layers with 256 and 128 neurons, respectively, each using Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation functions. Training was performed using the Adam optimizer, as implemented in *PyTorch*, over 10 epochs. The dataset was split such that 20% was allocated for testing, while 30% of the remaining training set was used for validation. The batch sizes were set to 256 for training, 128 for validation, and 1 for testing. A fixed learning rate of 0.01 was used, with no learning rate scheduler applied. The training process utilized the server's GPU, with CUDA as the designated computing device. These

parameters remained consistent throughout the evaluation presented in the following.

As shown in Table 7, the computational complexity of this metric, while not as low as that of PR-Scores or FD, remains significantly lower than that of ED. Notably, both feature dimensionality and number of samples have a clear impact on computation time.

Similar to PR-Scores, this metric fully benefits from dedicated hardware acceleration, particularly leveraging the GPU for efficient computation. It is also important to highlight that the primary computational burden stems from the training phase of the neural network. However, once trained, the model can be reused to evaluate new data without requiring retraining, provided that the meta-parameters of the data generation remain unchanged.

The values of this metric presented very little variance regardless of the feature extractor used to generate the datasets used in the evaluation. As consequence, we decided to not present the results using the same graphical aids of the other metrics but by simply reporting the mean and standard deviation of the numerical results over the three possible evaluations of interest. These are: 49.95% ($\pm 0.17\%$) for *same-real*, 49.99% ($\pm 0.06\%$) for *same-synth*, and 99.97% ($\pm 0.08\%$) for *mix*. Even with a relatively small and simple neural network architecture, this metric effectively differentiates between real and synthetic data distributions when compared against each other. Its performance in the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations aligns with expectations: since the input data originate from the same distribution, the network cannot achieve accuracy beyond random chance. However, this also implies that, unlike PR-Scores, this metric does not offer additional insights into the specific characteristics of the distributions being analyzed.

Overall, FCNNA effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic data, achieving near-perfect accuracy in the *mix* evaluation while behaving as expected in the *same-real* and *same-synth* cases. However, unlike PR-Scores, it provides no additional insights into distributional characteristics. Despite its reliance on neural network training, its strong discriminative power makes it a valuable metric for synthetic data validation.

C. DISCUSSION

The experimental evaluation conducted on the mammogram case study highlights the strengths and nuances of the *SynthVal* framework in the context of validating synthetic medical images. The results confirm that the metrics implemented in *SynthVal* are generally effective in detecting measurable distributional differences between real and synthetic data. In particular, *mix* evaluations consistently produce higher divergence scores than *same-real* or *same-synth* evaluations, indicating that the synthetic data distributions are reliably distinguishable from their real counterparts. These findings are further supported by the supplementary experimental evaluation reported in Appendix A, where *SynthVal* is tested on an additional medical image dataset and a generic image

dataset. The results suggest that its applicability may extend beyond the evaluation of mammograms or the specific model considered. Nevertheless, it should be noted that these outcomes are not necessarily guaranteed to generalize to new datasets or generative models. Moreover, while the metrics remain effective in distinguishing between real and synthetic data, a noticeable decline in performance can occur when they are applied to datasets with high visual heterogeneity – that is, collections containing images of vastly different objects.

Among the statistical similarity metrics, Fréchet Distance and Kullback–Leibler Divergence demonstrated a clear and consistent ability to distinguish real from synthetic data across a wide range of feature extractors, while maintaining a relatively favourable computational profile. Energy Distance also showed strong discriminative power, but its application was limited by higher computational demands – as clearly shown in Figure 12. On the other hand, Kernel Distance, while efficient, exhibited a lower level of sensitivity in certain configurations, particularly when distinguishing between *same-synth* and *mix* evaluations. This suggests that while it remains valuable, its effectiveness can depend heavily on the choice of feature extractor. Mean Mahalanobis Distance appears to be significantly less reliable than the other metrics in distinguishing between real and synthetic data, as further confirmed by the supplementary results presented in Appendix. Comparatively, it provides no meaningful advantage over alternative metrics with comparable computational complexity.

The inclusion of discriminative metrics such as Precision-Recall Scores and Fully Connected Neural Network Accuracy offered complementary perspectives. Precision-Recall Scores, in particular, proved highly reliable in highlighting both the overlap and diversity of synthetic datasets relative to real ones, and showed additional sensitivity to internal variability in data subsets – such as differences between *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations. The neural network accuracy metric, meanwhile, was especially effective in confirming separability between real and synthetic datasets through classification performance. However, its binary nature makes it less informative about finer-grained differences within the data distributions, and its dependence on hyperparameters choices may require careful tuning to prevent performance degradation, as evidenced by the results presented in Appendix.

Across the evaluations, the choice of feature extractor played a significant role in shaping the outcome. Feature representations derived from domain-specific models – particularly *rad-dino* and, to a lesser extent, the *MambaVision* family – generally provided more meaningful and discriminative embeddings for medical imaging tasks. This was evident in the improved metric performance when using these extractors.

It is important to emphasize that while the synthetic data evaluated in this study is often clearly distinguishable from real data based on the selected metrics, this observation does not inherently limit its applicability for downstream

use cases. The metrics employed by *SynthVal* are designed to capture subtle distributional or structural discrepancies that may be imperceptible to human observers or irrelevant in contexts such as model training or medical education. As such, distinguishability does not equate to ineffectiveness. Rather, it highlights the need to interpret validation results in light of the specific requirements and tolerances of the intended application.

It should also be noted that several of the metrics implemented in *SynthVal* require a substantial amount of data to yield reliable results and several may be computationally expensive. Consequently, they are not currently suitable for use within the training loop of generative models. Adapting them for such tasks represents an interesting direction for future research.

Overall, the experimental results confirm that *SynthVal* offers a robust, flexible, and insightful framework for evaluating synthetic data in medical imaging. Its ability to integrate multiple feature extractors and metrics allows for multi-angle assessments, enhancing interpretability and robustness. These findings support the broader applicability of *SynthVal* in synthetic data validation pipelines, and point to promising directions for future development – such as incorporating use-case-specific thresholds or integrating downstream performance evaluation.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented *SynthVal*, a modular and extensible framework for evaluating the quality of synthetic medical images using a diverse set of feature extractors and distributional similarity metrics. By focusing on the mammogram domain and leveraging the CSAW-CC dataset alongside synthetic images generated by a dedicated model, we demonstrated how *SynthVal* enables a fine-grained assessment of distributional alignment between real and synthetic data.

Our experiments show that several metrics – including Fréchet Distance, Kullback–Leibler Divergence, and PR-Scores – are effective in distinguishing between real and synthetic samples, particularly when paired with domain-specific feature extractors such as *rad-dino*. In contrast, metrics like MeanMD and Kernel Distance displayed lower sensitivity, and Wasserstein Distance was excluded due to high computational cost. The FCNNA metric confirmed the high separability between synthetic and real distributions, though it lacked nuance in distinguishing among real subsets.

The results underscore the critical role of feature extraction in shaping metric behaviour and demonstrate that well-designed synthetic image generators can still yield data distinguishable from real samples without compromising downstream utility. Finally, the framework’s GPU compatibility and modular architecture make it suitable for scalable and domain-adaptable validation pipelines.

Future work will focus on extending *SynthVal* to additional imaging modalities, refining metric thresholds based on application-specific requirements, and integrating down-

stream task evaluations to better assess the practical value of synthetic datasets.

APPENDIX

In this Appendix, we present an additional experimental evaluation using two datasets that include both real and synthetic images. The first is the Ultrasound (US) Simulation and Segmentation dataset⁷ [50], which contains 617 real abdominal ultrasound images collected from 11 subjects and 926 synthetically generated images. The second is the CIFAKE dataset [51], comprising 60,000 synthetic images – created using Stable Diffusion 1.4 – and 60,000 real images sourced from CIFAR-10 [52]. These images represent ten object and animal categories: birds, cars, cats, deer, dogs, frogs, horses, planes, ships, and trucks. The motivation behind this choice is twofold: first, to further evaluate *SynthVal* on a novel medical imaging dataset whose limited size allows for testing computationally demanding metrics – such as the Wasserstein Distance – and second, to explore whether *SynthVal* can be effectively applied beyond the medical imaging domain. Given the scope of this Appendix, we do not describe the datasets in detail; readers are referred to the cited references for further information.

FIGURE 13. Examples from the US dataset: on the left a real ultrasound, on the right one of the generated images.

FIGURE 14. Examples from the CIFAKE dataset: on the left a real image of a bird, on the right one of the generated images for the same class.

A. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The experimental setup closely follows the procedure described in Section V. Each dataset was divided into real and synthetic subsets, and their features were extracted using the same feature extractors employed in the main

⁷https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/ignaciorlando/ussimandsegm?select=abdominal_US

experimental evaluation. The resulting embeddings were then used to compute the selected metrics across three comparisons: real vs. real, synthetic vs. synthetic, and real vs. synthetic – corresponding to the *same-real*, *same-synth*, and *mix* configurations previously introduced. As in the main experiments, the *same* evaluations used two non-overlapping subsets of features. No additional random sampling or evaluations were performed beyond this setup.

The following Subsections present and discuss the results obtained for the two datasets under analysis.

1) US SIMULATION AND SEGMENTATION

Each metric is examined individually, following the same structure as the experimental evaluation described in Section V. We do not dwell on results that confirm the findings of the main evaluation; instead, we focus on outcomes that provide new or contrasting insights.

a: WASSERSTEIN DISTANCE

The results obtained for the Wasserstein Distance are particularly noteworthy, as this metric was too computationally demanding to be evaluated within the time constraints of the main experiments. As shown in Table 8, WD effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic distributions across all tested configurations. Notably, for the *dinov2-small*, *dinov2-base*, and *dinov2-large* feature extractors, WD values also differ substantially between the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations, suggesting that the metric may be capturing greater variability among synthetic samples.

TABLE 8. WD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. Column Features Extractor ID lists the identifier of the feature extractor used. Column Evaluation ID indicates the specific evaluation setup. Finally, columns Metric Value and Time present the value computed for the metric and the time needed for the evaluation, respectively. The symbol “.” denotes cases where all experiments for the corresponding sets failed to complete within the 1-hour timeout. The value of the Time column are expressed in seconds.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	11.78	6.68
	<i>same-real</i>	6.67	1.68
	<i>mix</i>	22.18	44.04
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	7.66	7.13
	<i>same-real</i>	4.38	1.74
	<i>mix</i>	14.28	44.14
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	13.08	6.80
	<i>same-real</i>	7.87	1.78
	<i>mix</i>	26.26	42.66
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	1.68	6.78
	<i>same-real</i>	1.55	1.75
	<i>mix</i>	3.85	44.28
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	1.12	6.90
	<i>same-real</i>	1.05	1.69
	<i>mix</i>	3.09	43.64
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	4.82	6.79
	<i>same-real</i>	5.15	1.66
	<i>mix</i>	12.09	44.71

The recorded execution times further illustrate the computational burden of WD. Considering that the dataset includes 617 real and 926 synthetic samples, the results clearly show a steep increase in computational cost with sample size. This significant growth explains why the Wasserstein Distance could not be feasibly computed within reasonable time limits for the much larger datasets used in the main experimental evaluation.

b: ENERGY DISTANCE

The results for the Energy Distance appear to confirm the findings reported in the main evaluation. As shown in Table 9, the metric effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic data, showing a clear separation even for features extracted using *dinov2-large* and *MambaVision-B-1K*. Notably, for these extractors, the *mix* evaluations – previously exceeding the timeout limit – were successfully completed in this experiment.

TABLE 9. ED values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.06	0.17
	<i>same-real</i>	0.08	0.07
	<i>mix</i>	17.87	0.53
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.05	0.25
	<i>same-real</i>	0.04	0.11
	<i>mix</i>	11.28	0.75
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.09	0.07
	<i>same-real</i>	0.09	0.03
	<i>mix</i>	21.00	0.20
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.01	0.25
	<i>same-real</i>	0.02	0.10
	<i>mix</i>	3.02	0.71
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.01	0.19
	<i>same-real</i>	0.01	0.08
	<i>mix</i>	2.95	0.53
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.03	0.17
	<i>same-real</i>	0.06	0.07
	<i>mix</i>	9.06	0.52

c: FRÉCHET DISTANCE

As shown in Table 10, the Fréchet Distance results appear to confirm the observations from the main experiment. For all feature extractors considered, the metric clearly differentiates between real and synthetic data. Interestingly, the DINO-based feature extractors also reveal a notable difference between the *same-real* and *same-synth* evaluations, suggesting that these models may capture the internal distribution characteristics of the samples more effectively.

d: KERNEL DISTANCE

As shown in Table 11, the results for the Kernel Distance are consistent with those observed in the main experimental evaluation. The *dinov2-small*, *dinov2-base*, and *dinov2-large* feature extractors produce embeddings that enable the metric to clearly distinguish between real and

TABLE 10. FD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	23.36	0.30
	<i>same-real</i>	10.70	0.29
	<i>mix</i>	434.45	0.25
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	11.53	0.67
	<i>same-real</i>	5.15	0.68
	<i>mix</i>	180.90	0.60
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	20.45	0.05
	<i>same-real</i>	12.17	0.07
	<i>mix</i>	611.05	0.05
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.48	0.69
	<i>same-real</i>	0.58	0.68
	<i>mix</i>	12.88	0.60
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.19	0.31
	<i>same-real</i>	0.28	0.28
	<i>mix</i>	8.62	0.27
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	3.30	0.30
	<i>same-real</i>	7.67	0.31
	<i>mix</i>	123.82	0.25

TABLE 11. KD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.01	1.33
	<i>same-real</i>	-0.01	0.63
	<i>mix</i>	19.55	2.30
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.01	1.59
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	0.72
	<i>mix</i>	3.84	2.59
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.03	1.06
	<i>same-real</i>	-0.15	0.51
	<i>mix</i>	164.79	1.83
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	1.57
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	0.86
	<i>mix</i>	0.03	2.62
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	1.35
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	0.63
	<i>mix</i>	0.03	2.28
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	1.32
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	0.65
	<i>mix</i>	0.59	2.20

synthetic data. Although the other extractors also allow for differentiation, the separation between the two distributions appears less pronounced. Notably, the increase in computational cost remains modest, rising from approximately 1 second for 617 samples to about 4 seconds for 24,696 samples in the main experiment.

e: KULLBACK-LEIBLER DIVERGENCE

As shown in Table 12, the results for the Kullback–Leibler Divergence are consistent with those reported in the main experiment. The metric successfully distinguishes between real and synthetic data across all feature extractors considered. The occurrence of negative values in some of the *same* evaluations can be attributed to the limited dataset size,

TABLE 12. KLD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	-4.16	0.09
	<i>same-real</i>	-10.37	0.06
	<i>mix</i>	878.43	0.19
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	-6.03	0.12
	<i>same-real</i>	-13.56	0.07
	<i>mix</i>	1079.32	0.26
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	-0.13	0.05
	<i>same-real</i>	4.85	0.03
	<i>mix</i>	467.92	0.10
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	8.00	0.12
	<i>same-real</i>	-25.32	0.07
	<i>mix</i>	990.81	0.31
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	3.55	0.09
	<i>same-real</i>	13.95	0.05
	<i>mix</i>	859.18	0.19
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	-6.93	0.10
	<i>same-real</i>	-40.79	0.05
	<i>mix</i>	762.30	0.19

TABLE 13. MeanMD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	35.61	0.06
	<i>same-real</i>	22.53	0.04
	<i>mix</i>	56.22	0.11
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	16.33	0.20
	<i>same-real</i>	7.88	0.09
	<i>mix</i>	29.09	0.17
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	60.39	0.01
	<i>same-real</i>	30.80	0.01
	<i>mix</i>	92.35	0.03
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.91	0.12
	<i>same-real</i>	0.83	0.07
	<i>mix</i>	0.87	0.17
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.38	0.07
	<i>same-real</i>	0.37	0.04
	<i>mix</i>	0.54	0.08
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	6.66	0.07
	<i>same-real</i>	11.56	0.04
	<i>mix</i>	10.92	0.10

which increases instability in the estimation process. This interpretation is supported by the values observed in the main experiment – much closer to zero – where a substantially larger number of samples was available.

f: MEAN MAHALANOBIS DISTANCE

As shown in Table 13, the results for the Mean Mahalanobis Distance appear overall weaker than those obtained in the main experiment. In particular, when applied to features extracted with MambaVision-B-1K and rad-dino, the metric yields higher values for the *same* evaluations than for the corresponding *mix* comparisons, indicating that it fails to clearly differentiate between real and synthetic data. This outcome is not entirely unexpected, as the MeanMD already

exhibited the weakest performance in the main experiments, and its limitations seem to be further amplified by the smaller sample size of the US dataset.

g: PRECISION AND RECALL SCORES

As shown in Tables 14 and 15, the PR-Score results are consistent with those observed in the main experiments: the metric effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic data across all feature extractors considered. Interestingly, when applied to embeddings from the MambaVision family of feature extractors, the PR-Score still detects differences in the *same* evaluations, although the values are closer than those obtained in the main experiments.

TABLE 14. P-Score values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.80	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.88	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.82	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.92	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.81	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.89	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.82	0.28
	<i>same-real</i>	0.88	0.35
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.68
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.78	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.86	0.18
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.47
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.82	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.95	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13

TABLE 15. R-Score values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.82	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.91	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.84	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.84	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.86	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.88	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.81	0.28
	<i>same-real</i>	0.87	0.35
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.68
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.83	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.91	0.18
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.47
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.81	0.11
	<i>same-real</i>	0.91	0.12
	<i>mix</i>	0.00	0.13

h: FCNN ACCURACY

As shown in Table 16, the FCNN Accuracy results closely mirror those from the main evaluation. The metric clearly distinguishes between real and synthetic data across all cases but does not offer additional insights into the internal characteristics of the respective distributions. The network architecture and hyperparameters are identical to those used in the main experiments.

2) CIFAKE

As with the previous dataset, each metric is analysed individually, following the same structure as the experimental evaluation described in Section V. We do not elaborate on results that merely confirm the findings of the main evaluation; instead, we focus on outcomes that reveal new or contrasting insights.

a: WASSERSTEIN DISTANCE

As expected, given the dataset size and previous results, the computation of the Wasserstein Distance for the samples of interest consistently exceeded the one-hour timeout limit.

b: ENERGY DISTANCE

As shown in Table 17, the computational complexity of the Energy Distance was too high to complete the *mix* evaluation – consisting of more than 100,000 samples – within the one-hour timeout, consistent with the insights gained from previous experiments. The results from the *same* evaluations align with those obtained in earlier tests but do not provide additional information regarding the metric's ability to distinguish between real and synthetic samples in the absence of the full set of evaluations.

c: FRÉCHET DISTANCE

As shown in Table 18, the results obtained with the Fréchet Distance are consistent with those from previous

TABLE 16. FCNNA values and computation times in the relevant cases for the US Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.50	2.36
	<i>same-real</i>	0.50	1.66
	<i>mix</i>	1.00	3.71
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.50	2.82
	<i>same-real</i>	0.50	1.98
	<i>mix</i>	1.00	4.61
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.50	1.71
	<i>same-real</i>	0.50	1.25
	<i>mix</i>	1.00	2.48
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.50	3.45
	<i>same-real</i>	0.50	4.18
	<i>mix</i>	1.00	4.62
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.50	2.47
	<i>same-real</i>	0.50	1.74
	<i>mix</i>	1.00	3.74
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.50	2.34
	<i>same-real</i>	0.45	1.68
	<i>mix</i>	1.00	3.71

TABLE 17. ED values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.01	2240.42
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	2240.90
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.01	3017.09
	<i>same-real</i>	0.01	3037.10
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	1114.02
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	1113.86
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	3037.07
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	3020.87
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	2239.71
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	2243.74
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	2251.76
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	2234.28
	<i>mix</i>	-	-

TABLE 18. FD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	14.30	0.87
	<i>same-real</i>	15.38	0.98
	<i>mix</i>	371.15	1.15
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	18.11	2.14
	<i>same-real</i>	20.78	2.10
	<i>mix</i>	375.93	1.90
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	7.11	0.51
	<i>same-real</i>	7.76	0.47
	<i>mix</i>	306.40	0.70
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.27	1.52
	<i>same-real</i>	0.30	1.87
	<i>mix</i>	10.62	1.91
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.16	0.82
	<i>same-real</i>	0.17	0.75
	<i>mix</i>	5.14	1.02
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.11	0.74
	<i>same-real</i>	0.09	0.68
	<i>mix</i>	8.22	0.99

experiments. Regardless of the embedding used, the FD consistently distinguishes clearly between real and synthetic data, although it seems to provide limited insight into the internal characteristics of the respective distributions.

d: KERNEL DISTANCE

As shown in Table 19, the Kernel Distance performs consistently with the results observed in previous experiments. Regardless of the feature extractor used to generate the embeddings, it reliably distinguishes between real and synthetic data, although it provides no additional insight in the *same* evaluations.

e: KULLBACK-LEIBLER DIVERGENCE

As shown in Table 20, the results for the Kullback-Leibler Divergence closely mirror those from the previous experi-

TABLE 19. KD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	3.37
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	3.13
	<i>mix</i>	0.69	3.17
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	3.60
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	3.87
	<i>mix</i>	0.31	4.06
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	2.47
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	2.49
	<i>mix</i>	4.36	2.57
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	3.69
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	3.89
	<i>mix</i>	2.18	3.64
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	3.18
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	3.08
	<i>mix</i>	1.95	3.20
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.00	3.13
	<i>same-real</i>	0.00	3.26
	<i>mix</i>	0.04	3.28

TABLE 20. KLD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	1.23	788.91
	<i>same-real</i>	-0.17	809.64
	<i>mix</i>	105.36	3235.95
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	-0.30	967.63
	<i>same-real</i>	1.70	988.49
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.37	520.72
	<i>same-real</i>	-0.14	542.12
	<i>mix</i>	49.61	2184.33
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	2.35	965.38
	<i>same-real</i>	1.17	991.81
	<i>mix</i>	-	-
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.45	784.08
	<i>same-real</i>	0.87	806.98
	<i>mix</i>	77.57	3244.33
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	1.41	786.39
	<i>same-real</i>	0.30	809.25
	<i>mix</i>	66.76	3255.76

ments. However, while the metric effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic data, its computational complexity caused the *mix* evaluations for *dinov2-large* and *MambaVision-B-1K* to exceed the one-hour timeout limit. It is also noteworthy that the larger number of samples appears to further stabilize the estimation algorithm, as indicated by the reduced magnitude of negative values compared with the earlier experiments.

f: MEAN MAHALANOBIS DISTANCE

As shown in Table 21, the results for the Mean Mahalanobis Distance are considerably weaker than those obtained in the other experiments. In no case does the metric clearly distinguish between real and synthetic data, consistently yielding higher values for the *same-synth* evaluations and showing no clear trend for the *same-real* or *mix* comparisons. While the MeanMD had already shown limited effectiveness

TABLE 21. MeanMD values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	233.02	1.51
	<i>same-real</i>	185.31	1.49
	<i>mix</i>	177.54	2.10
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	208.56	2.50
	<i>same-real</i>	161.74	2.02
	<i>mix</i>	154.35	4.85
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	246.55	0.57
	<i>same-real</i>	197.33	0.62
	<i>mix</i>	195.91	1.18
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	9.50	2.29
	<i>same-real</i>	8.97	2.23
	<i>mix</i>	8.62	4.44
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	5.26	1.45
	<i>same-real</i>	4.46	1.29
	<i>mix</i>	4.61	3.07
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	16.00	0.97
	<i>same-real</i>	13.55	1.40
	<i>mix</i>	15.14	1.79

in previous experiments, these results suggest that it should not be considered a reliable metric for differentiating between real and synthetic data – especially given the stronger performance of other metrics with comparable computational complexity. The poorer results are likely due to the greater heterogeneity within both the real and synthetic image sets, which include diverse object categories, in contrast to the relative uniformity of the ultrasound and mammogram datasets.

g: PRECISION AND RECALL SCORES

As shown in Tables 22 and 23, the PR-Scores – although slightly weaker than in the previous experiments – still effectively distinguish between real and synthetic data. We attribute this difference in performance to the greater heterogeneity of the CIFAKE dataset, which contrasts with the relative homogeneity of the ultrasound and mammogram datasets.

h: FCNN ACCURACY

As shown in Table 24, the FCNN Accuracy results closely mirror those from the previous experiments, except for the embeddings generated by the MambaVision family of feature extractors. Given the sensitivity of neural networks to hyperparameter configurations during training – and considering the consistent results obtained with other metrics using the same data and feature extractors – we interpret this discrepancy as an indication that the FCNN architecture and training parameters may require further tuning depending on the task at hand, rather than as evidence of a limitation in the feature extractors themselves.

B. DISCUSSION

Overall, the supplementary experimental evaluation supports and reinforces the findings presented in Section V. Among

TABLE 22. P-Score values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.75	0.72
	<i>same-real</i>	0.75	0.69
	<i>mix</i>	0.49	1.77
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.77	0.81
	<i>same-real</i>	0.75	0.81
	<i>mix</i>	0.53	2.07
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.78	0.62
	<i>same-real</i>	0.77	0.62
	<i>mix</i>	0.47	1.30
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.78	0.81
	<i>same-real</i>	0.76	0.80
	<i>mix</i>	0.59	2.00
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.76	0.72
	<i>same-real</i>	0.75	0.73
	<i>mix</i>	0.57	1.75
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.75	0.70
	<i>same-real</i>	0.73	0.71
	<i>mix</i>	0.49	1.76

TABLE 23. R-Score values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	<i>same-synth</i>	0.76	0.72
	<i>same-real</i>	0.74	0.69
	<i>mix</i>	0.21	1.77
dinov2-large	<i>same-synth</i>	0.76	0.81
	<i>same-real</i>	0.75	0.81
	<i>mix</i>	0.21	2.07
dinov2-small	<i>same-synth</i>	0.77	0.62
	<i>same-real</i>	0.77	0.62
	<i>mix</i>	0.22	1.30
MambaVision-B-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.78	0.81
	<i>same-real</i>	0.77	0.80
	<i>mix</i>	0.32	2.00
MambaVision-S-1K	<i>same-synth</i>	0.76	0.72
	<i>same-real</i>	0.75	0.73
	<i>mix</i>	0.32	1.75
rad-dino	<i>same-synth</i>	0.74	0.70
	<i>same-real</i>	0.74	0.71
	<i>mix</i>	0.62	1.76

the most noteworthy results are those obtained for the Wasserstein Distance on the Ultrasound dataset. These experiments confirm that, although the metric’s computational cost increases sharply with the number of samples, it effectively distinguishes between real and synthetic data. Moreover, for some feature extractors, the Wasserstein Distance appears to capture meaningful information about the internal structure of the two distributions, providing insights beyond mere discrimination. Another key finding concerns the Mean Mahalanobis Distance, which proves to be less reliable than initially expected. It fails to offer any substantial advantage over other metrics with comparable computational complexity – such as the PR-Scores, Kernel Distance, or Fréchet Distance – and, in several cases, performs noticeably worse.

Finally, it is worth noting that, despite the CSAW-CC and Ultrasound datasets containing higher-resolution and more

TABLE 24. FCNNA values and computation times in the relevant cases for the CIFAKE Dataset. See Table 8 for more details.

Features Extractor ID	Evaluation ID	Metric Value	Time
dinov2-base	same-synth	0.50	160.48
	same-real	0.50	160.67
	mix	0.96	327.51
dinov2-large	same-synth	0.50	235.52
	same-real	0.50	219.48
	mix	0.97	475.22
dinov2-small	same-synth	0.50	102.99
	same-real	0.50	107.06
	mix	0.97	232.43
MambaVision-B-1K	same-synth	0.50	199.51
	same-real	0.50	235.57
	mix	0.50	434.99
MambaVision-S-1K	same-synth	0.50	163.92
	same-real	0.50	162.13
	mix	0.50	384.61
rad-dino	same-synth	0.50	189.09
	same-real	0.50	173.21
	mix	0.91	324.68

complex medical images, several metrics exhibit weaker performance on the CIFAKE dataset, which consists of comparatively simple 28×28 -pixel images. We attribute this to the greater heterogeneity of CIFAKE, whose images represent a wide range of unrelated object categories – from birds to ships to cars – introducing considerable variability in visual content. Indeed, since the feature extractors already account for pixel-level and resolution-related complexity when generating embeddings, the decrease in performances likely stems from the diverse semantic and structural characteristics of the CIFAKE images, which make their feature distributions more challenging to model and compare consistently.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Khosravi, F. Li, T. Dapamede, P. Rouzrokh, C. U. Gamble, H. M. Trivedi, C. C. Wyles, A. B. Sellergren, S. Purkayastha, B. J. Erickson, and J. W. Gichoya, "Synthetically enhanced: Unveiling synthetic data's potential in medical imaging research," *eBioMedicine*, vol. 104, Jun. 2024, Art. no. 105174.
- [2] V. C. Pezoulas, D. I. Zaridis, E. Mylona, C. Androutsos, K. Apostolidis, N. S. Tachos, and D. I. Fotiadis, "Synthetic data generation methods in healthcare: A review on open-source tools and methods," *Comput. Structural Biotechnol. J.*, vol. 23, pp. 2892–2910, Dec. 2024.
- [3] M. Ibrahim, Y. A. Khalil, S. Amirrajab, C. Sun, M. Breeuwer, J. Pluim, B. Elen, G. Ertaylan, and M. Dumontier, "Generative AI for synthetic data across multiple medical modalities: A systematic review of recent developments and challenges," *Comput. Biol. Med.*, vol. 189, May 2025, Art. no. 109834.
- [4] A. Duminil, S.-S. Ieng, and D. Gruyer, "Assessing fidelity in synthetic datasets: A multi-criteria combination methodology," in *Proc. 27th Int. Conf. Inf. Fusion (FUSION)*, Venice, Italy, Jul. 2024, pp. 1–8.
- [5] V. B. Vallevik, A. Babic, S. E. Marshall, S. Elvatun, H. M. B. Brøgger, S. Alagaratnam, B. Edwin, N. R. Veeraragavan, A. K. Befring, and J. F. Nygård, "Can i trust my fake data—A comprehensive quality assessment framework for synthetic tabular data in healthcare," *Int. J. Med. Informat.*, vol. 185, May 2024, Art. no. 105413.
- [6] A. Figueira and B. Vaz, "Survey on synthetic data generation, evaluation methods and GANs," *Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 15, p. 2733, Aug. 2022.
- [7] D. Guidotti. (Oct. 2025). *SynthVal*. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17284606>
- [8] K. Dembrower, P. Lindholm, and F. Strand, "A multi-million mammography image dataset and population-based screening cohort for the training and evaluation of deep neural networks—The cohort of screened women (CSAW)," *J. Digit. Imag.*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 408–413, Apr. 2020.
- [9] R. Montoya-Del-Angel, K. Sam-Millan, J. C. Vilanova, and R. Martí, "MAM-E: Mammographic synthetic image generation with diffusion models," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 7, p. 2076, Mar. 2024.
- [10] C. Z. Mooney, *Monte Carlo Simulation*. Newbury Park, CA, USA: Sage, 1997.
- [11] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio, "Generative adversarial networks," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 63, no. 11, pp. 139–144, 2020.
- [12] N. K. Singh and K. Raza, "Medical image generation using generative adversarial networks: A review," in *Health Informatics: A Computational Perspective in Healthcare*. Singapore: Springer, 2021, pp. 77–96.
- [13] H. Li, S. Yu, and J. C. Principe, "Causal recurrent variational autoencoder for medical time series generation," in *Proc. AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell.*, 2023, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 8562–8570.
- [14] A. Kazerouni, E. K. Aghdam, M. Heidari, R. Azad, M. Fayyaz, I. Hacihaliloglu, and D. Merhof, "Diffusion models in medical imaging: A comprehensive survey," *Med. Image Anal.*, vol. 88, Aug. 2023, Art. no. 102846.
- [15] J. Ho, A. Jain, and P. Abbeel, "Denosing diffusion probabilistic models," in *Proc. Annu. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. NeurIPS*, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–13.
- [16] P. Esser, S. Kulal, A. Blattmann, R. Entezari, J. Müller, H. Saini, Y. Levi, D. Lorenz, A. Sauer, F. Boesel, D. Podell, T. Dockhorn, Z. English, K. Lacey, A. Goodwin, Y. Marek, and R. Rombach, "Scaling rectified flow transformers for high-resolution image synthesis," in *Proc. Forty-first Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2024, pp. 12606–12633.
- [17] J. Yoon, D. Jarrett, and M. Van der Schaar, "Time-series generative adversarial networks," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 32, 2019, pp. 1–10.
- [18] T. Karras, S. Laine, and T. Aila, "A style-based generator architecture for generative adversarial networks," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Jun. 2019, pp. 4401–4410.
- [19] S. Lee, E. Park, H. Yi, and S. H. Lee, "StRDAN: Synthetic-to-real domain adaptation network for vehicle re-identification," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. Workshops (CVPRW)*, Seattle, WA, USA, Jun. 2020, pp. 2590–2597.
- [20] M. Hittmeir, A. Ekelhart, and R. Mayer, "Utility and privacy assessments of synthetic data for regression tasks," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Big Data (Big Data)*, Los Angeles, CA, USA, Dec. 2019, pp. 5763–5772.
- [21] Z. Wang, A. C. Bovik, H. R. Sheikh, and E. P. Simoncelli, "Image quality assessment: From error visibility to structural similarity," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600–612, Apr. 2004.
- [22] Q. Huynh-Thu and M. Ghanbari, "Scope of validity of PSNR in image/video quality assessment," *Electron. Lett.*, vol. 44, no. 13, pp. 800–801, Jun. 2008.
- [23] R. Zhang, P. Isola, A. A. Efros, E. Shechtman, and O. Wang, "The unreasonable effectiveness of deep features as a perceptual metric," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.*, Salt Lake City, UT, USA, Jun. 2018, pp. 586–595.
- [24] L. V. Kantorovich, "The mathematical method of production planning and organization," *Manage. Sci.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 363–422, 1939.
- [25] C. Villani, *The Wasserstein Distances*. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2009, pp. 93–111.
- [26] M. Arjovsky, S. Chintala, and L. Bottou, "Wasserstein generative adversarial networks," in *Proc. 34th Int. Conf. Mach. Learn. (ICML)*, vol. 70, Sydney, NSW, Australia, Aug. 2017, pp. 214–223.
- [27] S. Kullback and R. A. Leibler, "On information and sufficiency," *Ann. Math. Statist.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 79–86, 1951.
- [28] H. Alt and M. Godau, "Computing the Fréchet distance between two polygonal curves," *Int. J. Comput. Geom. Appl.*, vol. 5, nos. 1–2, pp. 75–91, Nov. 1995.
- [29] M. Heusel, H. Ramsauer, T. Unterthiner, B. Nessler, and S. Hochreiter, "GANs trained by a two time-scale update rule converge to a local Nash equilibrium," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. Annu. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 30, 2017, pp. 6626–6637.

- [30] M. L. Rizzo and G. J. Székely, "Energy distance," *WIREs Comput. Stat.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 27–38, 2015.
- [31] J. M. Phillips and S. Venkatasubramanian, "A gentle introduction to the kernel distance," 2011, *arXiv:1103.1625*.
- [32] M. P. Chandra et al., "On the generalised distance in statistics," *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India USA*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 49–55, 1936.
- [33] T. Kynkäänniemi, T. Karras, S. Laine, J. Lehtinen, and T. Aila, "Improved precision and recall metric for assessing generative models," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. 32: Annu. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 32, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2019, pp. 3927–3936.
- [34] A. D. Lautrup, T. Hyrup, A. Zimek, and P. Schneider-Kamp, "Syntheval: A framework for detailed utility and privacy evaluation of tabular synthetic data," *Data Mining Knowl. Discovery*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 1–25, Jan. 2025.
- [35] G. Santangelo, G. Nicora, R. Bellazzi, and A. Dagliati, "How good is your synthetic data? SynthRO, a dashboard to evaluate and benchmark synthetic tabular data," *BMC Med. Informat. Decis. Making*, vol. 25, no. 1, p. 89, Feb. 2025.
- [36] Z. Qian, B.-C. Cebere, and M. V. D. Schaar, "Synthcity: Facilitating innovative use cases of synthetic data in different data modalities," *CoRR*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.07573>
- [37] FAICOS. (2024). *PyMDMA: Multimodal Data Metrics for Auditing Real and Synthetic Datasets*. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/fraunhoferportugal/pymdma>
- [38] A. Paszke et al., "PyTorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. 32: Annu. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 32, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2019, pp. 8026–8037.
- [39] S. Demarchi, D. Guidotti, L. Pulina, and A. Tacchella, "NeVer2: Learning and verification of neural networks," *Soft Comput.*, vol. 28, no. 19, pp. 11647–11665, Oct. 2024.
- [40] F. Pérez-García, H. Sharma, S. Bond-Taylor, K. Bouzid, V. Salvatelli, M. Ilse, S. Bannur, D. C. Castro, A. Schwaighofer, M. P. Lungren, M. Wetscherek, N. Codella, S. L. Hyland, J. Alvarez-Valle, and O. Oktay, "RAD-DINO: Exploring scalable medical image encoders beyond text supervision," 2024, *arXiv:2401.10815*.
- [41] M. Oquab et al., "DINOv2: Learning robust visual features without supervision," *Trans. Mach. Learn. Res.*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=a68SUt6zFt>
- [42] A. Hatamizadeh and J. Kautz, "MambaVision: A hybrid mamba-transformer vision backbone," 2025, *arXiv:2407.08083*.
- [43] T. Wolf, L. Debut, V. Sanh, J. Chaumond, C. Delangue, A. Moi, P. Cistac, T. Rault, R. Louf, M. Funtowicz, and J. Brew, "Hugging-face's transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing," 2019, *arXiv:1910.03771*.
- [44] C. R. Harris et al., "Array programming with NumPy," *Nature*, vol. 585, no. 7825, pp. 357–362, 2020.
- [45] W. McKinney, "Data structures for statistical computing in Python," in *Proc. 9th Python Sci. Conf. (SciPy)*, Austin, TX, USA, S. van der Walt and J. Millman, Eds., Jun. 2010, pp. 56–61.
- [46] F. Pérez-Cruz, "Kullback–Leibler divergence estimation of continuous distributions," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Inf. Theory*, Toronto, ON, Canada, Jul. 2008, pp. 1666–1670.
- [47] G. J. Székely, M. L. Rizzo, and N. K. Bakirov, "Measuring and testing dependence by correlation of distances," *Ann. Statist.*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 2769–2794, Dec. 2007.
- [48] C. Szegedy, V. Vanhoucke, S. Ioffe, J. Shlens, and Z. Wojna, "Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 2818–2826.
- [49] R. Rombach, A. Blattmann, D. Lorenz, P. Esser, and B. Ommer, "High-resolution image synthesis with latent diffusion models," 2021, *arXiv:2112.10752*.
- [50] S. Vitale, J. I. Orlando, E. Iarussi, and I. Larrabide, "Improving realism in patient-specific abdominal ultrasound simulation using CycleGANs," *Int. J. Comput. Assist. Radiol. Surgery*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 183–192, Feb. 2020.
- [51] J. J. Bird and A. Lotfi, "CIFAKE: Image classification and explainable identification of AI-generated synthetic images," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 15642–15650, 2024.
- [52] A. Krizhevsky, "Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images," Dept. Comput. Sci., Univ. Toronto, Toronto, ON, Canada, Tech. Rep., 2009.

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